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Adriana Jubilado

[REDACTED]
Date: 19/12/2025

Declaration of own work

I hereby declare that

1. This work is composed by me.
2. This work has not been accepted in any previous application for a degree or diploma by me or anyone else.
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Name and Student Number:

Adriana Jubilado, [REDACTED]

Date:

19/12/2025

Place:

Leeuwarden, Netherlands

Signature:

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Abstract

In recent years, the tourism industry has increasingly shown attention towards ethical tourism. This shift has been highly influenced by Gen Z rising awareness and knowledge towards ethical practices, as well as their recognition of the negative consequences of unethical tourism. However, despite this growing awareness, a discrepancy remains between ethical intentions and actual behaviour. This dissertation explored this issue by addressing the problem statement: “What are the constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?”.

The literature review analysed essential concepts to this research, including the specific interpretation of ethics based on virtue ethics framework, the attitude-behaviour gap, and the constraints that shape individual’s ethical actions. Through the use of the Theory of constraints, three main types of barriers were identified: intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural. These insights framed the research design, which utilized in-depth interviews, complemented by a supplementary workshop.

The findings of the research showcase the student’s experiences when attempting to practice ethical tourism and reveal the constraints that impedes them from doing so. Intrapersonal constraints emerged when participants identified personal limitations, highlighting that individual needs often aim higher than ethical intentions. Interpersonal constraints were also found to be highly influential, as the surrounding environment strongly shapes student’s perceptions and behaviours on ethical tourism. Within this category, social media influence was discovered to be a new highly impactful factor on shaping Gen Z travel decisions. Finally, structural constraints were employed when individuals described external barriers such as insufficient information or financial limitations, which many are shaped by the tourism industry itself.

Based on these findings, this dissertation presents several recommendations for future research and for the tourism industry. Future studies could expand methodological approaches by incorporating quantitative methods, exploring additional demographic groups, and incorporate experimental and observational techniques to further validate the insights of this research. For the tourism industry, it is recommended that organizations develop budget-friendly ethical tourism options to contradict the structural barriers identified in this research. This involve aligning prices of ethical alternatives with those of regular offerings and improving transparency through the strategic use of social media to clearly communicate the value of their ethical options.

Key words: Ethical tourism; Gen Z; Constraints; Intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural barriers; Virtue Ethics; Attitude-behaviour gap

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1. Context

Tourism is an industry that people have included in their daily life's. More and more individuals look every year for famous sites to go explore, or "unknown" places that they can have the privilege to visit. However, with the growth of the industry, tourism has not only become a popular industry, but also the synonym for negative consequences in many communities, these being at environmental, social, and financial level (Thullah & Jalloh, 2021). In the recent years, people have become aware and gained knowledge towards these challenges, raising ethical concerns. According to Zebardast (2019), ethical concerns in tourism are related to the environmental, social, and economic impacts. These impacts include environmental degradation (pollution), displacement of local people, disrespecting indigenous communities, unfair labour situations, violation of human rights, economic dependence on tourism, and many other ethical challenges. With the globalized world that we live in, individuals need to be mindful towards their impact on the world, and specially, their impact while travelling (Baloch et al., 2022). In essence, the future of the tourism industry depends truly on individual's commitment to practicing an ethical tourism (World Economic Forum & KEARNEY, 2025).

Gen Z is distinguished from other generations for its responsible mindset of what their impact might cause in the world (Jayatissa, 2023). This generation have grown in the peak of social media and technology, resulting in being constantly exposed to what is happening and new information (Tirocchi, 2024). However, this constant exposure has created "intention" in Gen Z (Djafarova & Fouts, 2022). The intention to change what is the imminent future of the tourism industry, in hopes that an ethical tourism is the answer. Additionally, it is equally important for individuals to acknowledge this solution, as well as the Gen Z studying tourism: these individuals are the future of the tourism industry. It is crucial that the future of the industry fully aligns with ethical practices, and it is committed to standardized ethical travel (World Economic Forum & KEARNEY, 2025; *Global Code of Ethics for Tourism*, n.d.)

Despite positive attitude of Gen Z towards ethical tourism, many appear to encounter multiple limitations that prevent them from acting according to their intentions (Juvan & Dolnicar, 2014). These barriers are called "constraints". Constraints are obstacles that impede individual's intentions to become an outcome (Dutta, 2023). With that being said, it is crucial to identify what these constraints are (towards ethical tourism) in order to surpass them and achieve an ethical tourism industry.

1.2. Focus of Dissertation

This research aims to identify and discuss the constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face when practicing ethical tourism. Seyfi et al. (2024) propose a framework that categorizes these constraints into three major themes named as intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural, each of which includes several sub-themes. The present dissertation applies this framework to Generation Z students at NHL Stenden University in Leeuwarden, Netherlands, with the objectives of evaluating its credibility and determining whether it can be further developed. Specifically, this research focuses on examining the intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural constraints experienced by these students in their efforts to practice ethical tourism.

1.3. Main Topics

This paper aims to identify and critically discuss several key topics relevant to ethical tourism, with a particular focus on understanding why Gen Z (specifically tourism students at NHL Stenden) struggle to consistently engage in ethical tourism despite holding strong ethical values. The topics addressed are interconnected and aligned with the central theme of this research: the constraints faced by Gen Z in practicing ethical tourism. These discussions are presented to provide a systematic foundation for analysis.

The first topic examined is ethics, as it is essential to establish a clear understanding of ethics in general and, more specifically, ethics within the tourism context. Without this ethical lens, the concept of “constraints” would lose its meaning, as these constraints represent specific barriers that block individuals from acting in accordance with ethical intentions (Mishra & Moktan, 2019). However, defining ethics presents itself a challenge, as it is often regarded as a controversial and complex concept. Ethics is commonly understood as the study of “right and wrong” but since universal definitions of right and wrong lack clarity, ethics encompasses broad and overlapping ideas (Gbadamosi, 2004). For the purpose of this dissertation, the virtue principle will be adopted. As Manthiou and Kuppelwieser (2025) explain, the virtue principle is when “tourism can be classified as either a virtue or a vice” (p.2): tourism offers sustainable tourism alternatives which are virtues, as well as, mass tourism options, which are vices. This principle is crucial for this research since it directly analysis the constraints that forces individual’s to not act conforming their intentions. In other words, while other frameworks are just focused on an action being ethical, the virtue principle understands why people might want to act responsibly (virtue) but still end up making harmful choices (vice) (Jamal, 2004).

Secondly, the target group will be discussed as they are the grabbing point of discussion for this research. It is important to understand Gen Z's ethical intentions in comparison to their actual behaviour, in order to evaluate the discrepancy. According to D'Acunto et al. (2025) Gen Z are often presented as socially and environmentally active in matters of ethical consumption, as they express a sense of identity through prioritizing sustainability in their lifestyle choices, including in the tourism context where travellers, in theory, place high importance on sustainable practices and environmental issues. However, it was also shown that, in reality, Gen Z's (tourism) behaviour is often driven away to what they express (Minazzi & Grechi, 2025). Seyfi et al. (2024) argue that this generation holds an idealized and optimistic view of its ethical commitments, which can become unachievable when confronted with real-world complexities. Furthermore, as a generation that is conscious of societal challenges, such as environmental crises, financial pressures and human rights issues (due to social media, globalization, and more), Gen Z feels a heightened responsibility to act ethically (Lopes et al., 2024). At the same time, they are burdened by the dual challenge of suffering from these global issues while being expected to drive solutions. The tension between their ethical aspirations and practical realities can be conceptualized as constraints, which form the core focus of this research. In addition, in order for the research of this dissertation to be specific, the focus is on the Gen Z at NHL Stenden students as the primary research group. This population was chosen considering accessibility and relevant research population, since the body reflects multiple cultural backgrounds and international perspectives, adding to the reliability and validity of the research. In addition, tourism management students are specifically included in this target group, for the purpose of relying on the informed perspectives of the future professionals of the tourism industry.

The third and final topic explored relates to constraints. According to Cambridge University Press (n.d.), constraints are defined as "something that controls what you do by keeping you within particular limits. ". In the context of ethical tourism, constraints refer to the factors that prevent Gen Z from aligning their ethical intentions with their actions. Rahman's (1998) Theory of Constrains provides a valuable framework for analysing these barriers. The theory identifies three dimensions of constraints: intrapersonal (internal factors), interpersonal (social factors), and structural (external factors). This framework will be applied to identify and categorize the obstacles faced by Gen Z at NHL Stenden when engaging in ethical tourism. Furthermore, this research will analyse how these different forms of constraints interact and reinforce one another.

Consequently, this dissertation addresses three interrelated topics: ethics, the ethical orientations and behaviours of Generation Z, and the constraints that shape their ability to act ethically within tourism contexts. Together, these discussions provide a comprehensive foundation for understanding the challenges Gen Z encounters when attempting to practice ethical tourism.

1.4. Relevance

As outlined in the introduction, tourism is an industry facing significant challenges to its long-term survival if it does not facilitate itself for transformation towards sustainability. At the same time, it is an industry that cannot simply cease to exist, given its global economic, social, and cultural relevance. Current discussions in the tourism field often emphasize how consumers (Gen Z) can practice ethical tourism, yet less papers address the constraints that prevent them from doing so. This paper seeks then to address this gap by examining the barriers faced by Generation Z students at NHL Stenden, Leeuwarden, when engaging with ethical tourism.

This dissertation shares its relevance in three different formats. Firstly, from an academic perspective, existing literature normally focuses on understanding the motivations for practicing ethical tourism, rather than underlying the constraints that individuals encounter when trying to engage in ethical travel. Given the significant impact of unethical tourism on social, economic, and environmental aspects, this research is contributing to the urgent need for more studies on this matter. From a practical perspective, the research identifies the specific constraints experienced by the target group in attempting to practice ethical tourism. This understanding is crucial for designing strategies to reduce these barriers and promote more consistent ethical engagement. Finally, from a societal perspective, this research addresses two critical issues: the rise of an ethical concern generation and its interactions with urgent global challenges in the tourism industry.

1.5. Problem Statement

For the purpose of this research, the following problem statement was designed:

“What are the constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?”.

This problem statement was formulated to directly engage with the complex challenges of practicing ethical tourism within a clearly defined and researchable context. Its primary intent is to align with the overall objective of this research by examining the gap between the ethical

intention expressed by Gen Z and their actual tourism behaviour. Instead of giving advice on how this generation should practice ethical tourism, this research focuses on uncovering the constraints that prevent intentions to become behaviour.

Furthermore, the problem statement specifically situates this research within the context of Gen Z at NHL Stenden. This framing is deliberate, as Generation Z is widely recognized for its reputation as a value-driven and sustainability-oriented generation. At the same time, NHL Stenden Gen Z students provide both an accessible and relevant target group.

1.6. Aim & Objectives

The aim of this research is to get insights and discuss the intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face when practicing ethical tourism. By researching and understanding the challenges this target group face in ethical tourism, it will consequently present the different factors that impact ethical tourism practices. The following objectives have been determined in order to obtain insights into the constraints that Gen Z at NHL Stenden face when practicing ethical tourism:

1. To examine the **intrapersonal constraints** that influence Gen Z at NHL Stenden in practicing ethical tourism.
2. To examine the **interpersonal constraints** that influence Gen Z at NHL Stenden in practicing ethical tourism.
3. To examine the **structural constraints** that influence Gen Z at NHL Stenden in practicing ethical tourism.

1.7. Dissertation Outline

This dissertation presents several topics divided into its specific chapters.

The first step of the dissertation is presented in chapter 1, named as the introduction. This chapter introduces the research topic, context, and the focus of the dissertation. Additionally, the main topics and the relevance of this research are outlined in this chapter, as well as the problem statement and the aim and objectives of the dissertation.

Chapter 2 corresponds to the literature review of concepts related to this dissertation. Such topics are the general definition of ethics and ethics in tourism, where it is explored the virtue principal framework. Furthermore, an explanation of Generation Z is exposed. Consequently, a connection between this generation and their ethical values is formed, in which the attitude-

behaviour gap model is presented. At the end of the literature review chapter, constraints and the Constraints Theory is going to be explained, which includes the intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural constraints.

Furthermore, chapter 3 covers the methodology. In other words, is going to explain the conceptual model, research questions and problem statement, research approach, the population and sample, the data collection methods, the data analysis approach, as well as the validity, reliability, and limitations.

Chapter 4 presents the findings of this dissertation. These findings which will be positioned under three main categories of constraints: intrapersonal, interpersonal constraints, and structural constraints. The results will be evaluated using coding methods. Additionally, a discussion of the findings will be conducted in this same chapter, where it will be exposed all the constraints that are inherently limited participants to participate in ethical tourism.

At the end of the dissertation, in chapter 5, the conclusions of the dissertation are presented in order to respond to the research's problem statement, as well as coherent recommendations for future research and for the tourism industry.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1. Introduction of Literature Review

The following literature review has the purpose of reviewing existing academic research about constraints that Gen Z at NHL Stenden face when practicing ethical tourism. The chapter is structured into three main themes to provide a comprehensive understanding of the literature relevant to this dissertation.

Firstly, the chapter explores ethics in tourism, explaining the relevance of ethics within a globalized and culturally diverse industry. This section also justifies the adoption of virtue ethics as the most suitable theoretical framework for this study. Secondly, it analyses Gen Z's ethical intentions and values, highlighting the attitude-behaviour gap that explains why ethical intentions are not always translated into actual behaviour. Thirdly, the chapter introduces the Theory of Constraints framework to identify and situate the limitations of ethical tourism. Finally, an indicator matrix is included at the end of the chapter to summarize indicators and inform the interview design.

Overall, this literature review established the theoretical foundation for the research and directly addresses the dissertation's problem statement: "What are the constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?".

2.2. Ethics in Tourism

Ethics, one of the main themes of this research, can be defined as the examination of human actions through the lens of "good" and "evil". This concept establishes whether an action is considered "morally right" or "morally wrong", thereby shaping individual's daily decisions and behaviours (Bartneck et al., 2020). However, ethical definitions vary depending on societies, as they are influenced by cultural, contextual, and physiological factors, particularly in today's globalized world (Collste, 2017).

Tourism, by its very nature, is an industry that depends on globalization and cultural exchange. As a sector that brings people with different values together, makes ethics an important topic of discussion (Tolkach, 2024). Ethics in tourism is related to multiple ethical concerns about human rights, borders, climate change, disability, labour, indigenous communities, and more (Taheri et al., 2024). However, besides many efforts to address these concerns, applying ethical principles in tourism remains complex, as what is seen as morally correct in one culture may

differ in another, often leading to clashes that affect both hosts and visitors (Banaszkiewicz & Buczkowska, 2014). For example, while elephant riding is accepted in some destinations, many Western tourists view it as unethical (Flower et al., 2021). In theory, ethical principles in tourism may appear straightforward, but their practical application is far more challenging (Weeden, 2005).

This tension highlights the core problem of this research: although consumers, particularly Gen Z, express intentions to participate in ethical tourism, these intentions are not always translated into actual behaviour.

2.2.1. The virtue ethics

To better understand why intentions do not always translate into behaviour, it is useful to examine established ethical theories. Teleology and deontology are briefly introduced in this paraphrase with the mere purpose of providing context, but this research ultimately adopts the virtue principle, as it will be explained further.

Teleology evaluates the morality of actions based on their results or consequences, while Deontology judge actions by their compliance to moral duties or rules, regardless of the outcomes (Manthiou & Kuppelwieser, 2025). By contrast, Virtue Ethics is particularly significant in this dissertation because it puts the focus on the moral character and the pursuit of virtues, rather than rules and consequences (Dzwonkowska, 2024). Within tourism, this perspective associate sustainable practices such as ecotourism and slow tourism with virtues, while mass tourism is often associated with vices that produce negative consequences for the environment, destinations, and host communities (Manthiou & Kuppelwieser, 2025). As Wijesinghe (2013) argues, ethical tourism depends on individual's commitment to virtuous practices, requiring the capacity to make judgments in the right context, at the right time, and in the right way. Therefore, this framework is centred on the moral agent intentions and their ability to align actions with virtue, rather than on rigid rules and norms (Dzwonkowska, 2024).

Accordingly, this research adopts virtue ethics as its ethical perspective on ethical tourism. The problem statement highlights the constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face when attempting to practice ethical tourism. These challenges are not simple questions of following moral rules (deontology) or securing perfect outcomes (teleology), but rather questions of values, intentions, and the challenges of living up to ethical ideals (Jamal, 2004). Virtue ethics directly relates to this reality by focusing on the ethical intention of the individual, acknowledging the

gap between intention and practice, and recognizing the influence of constraints in shaping ethical behaviour. On the other hand, the other theoretical frameworks described would risk overlooking these limitations: if an individual fails to meet a rule or a specific outcome, its behaviour would be directly considered “unethical”, without addressing the reasons (constraints) of why the individual (Gen Z at NHL Stenden) may struggle to act according to its intentions.

Therefore, ethical tourism should be understood as a balance between ideals and constraints, for which virtue ethics provides the most suitable perspective.

2.3. Gen Z: Attitude-Behaviour Gap

Generations are often identified by assigning specific age groups to corresponding generational labels. However, this approach alone is insufficient: generations are not merely chronological categories, but rather shaped by shared lifestyles, attitudes, and socio-cultural influences that appear within a specific historical and global context (Seyfi et al., 2024). Gen Z represents a unique group: born during the digital era, this generation grew up surrounded by mobile devices, social media, and constant internet connectivity, never experiencing a world without digital technologies. Nevertheless, being raised in a globalized and interconnected world, has exposed Gen Z to constant global issues such as environmental sustainability, terrorism, and human behaviour’s impact on the planet (Commission, 2020). These influences strongly shaped Gen Z’s values, attitudes, and beliefs, particularly regarding collective action, sustainability, and ethical consumption.

Research indicates that members of Gen Z are conscious of their decision’s impact, expressing a preference for ethical choices in areas such as tourism (Seyfi et al., 2025). Nonetheless, while individuals express positive attitudes towards ethical practices, it is not always translated into behavioural outcomes, resulting in what is commonly referred to as the attitude-behaviour gap (Juvan & Dolnicar, 2014). This gap refers to the constraints that prevent individuals from aligning their ethical intentions with actual behaviour. Such constraints include that other issues have greater importance, expressing no alternatives to current behaviours, using escape and relaxation as an excuse for ignoring environmental considerations, not being correctly informed about vacations alternatives that come at a low environmental cost, justifying non-sustainable behaviour while traveling by claiming that their environmental friendly engagement at home are sufficient, being too occupied to change behaviours, tendency to shift responsibility onto others (Pulido-Fernández et al., 2024), having hope in technology solutions, denying responsibility,

financial limitations and expensive tourism services (Konieczna & Trybuś-Borowiecka, 2025), time pressures, highlighting industries benefits from carbon-emitting options, and saying that there is little impact from personal behaviour (Juvan & Dolnicar, 2014). Additionally, Minazzi and Grechi (2025) has also concluded that factors such as compensating unethical behaviour through other benefits of tourism, convenience preferences and social pressures serve as important constraints to consider. In this sense, intention alone is a poor predictor of behaviour, as consumers intentions does not always align with what they do in reality (Untarini, 2020).

Understanding the attitude-behaviour gap is central to this dissertation, as it highlights the challenges Gen Z at NHL Stenden face when attempting to practice ethical tourism.

2.4. Constraints

In recent years, growing attention has been directed towards the challenges that tourism poses to society, the environment, and the economy. This increasing awareness is generally considered positive, as consumers attempt to include their knowledge into everyday practices (Ting et al., 2023). This shift is particularly evident in the tourism industry, since tourists increasingly seek opportunities to engage in ethical tourism (Humagain & Singleton, 2021). However, research demonstrates that many individuals encounter significant barriers that impeded them from doing so (Seyfi et al., 2024). These barriers are referred to as constraints.

Constraints can be understood as bottlenecks, defined as any circumstance that prevents an intention from achieving its intended purpose (Dale et al., 2012). Within the context of ethical tourism, constraints represent the barriers and limitations that prevent consumers from practicing ethical travel, even if they express intention to do so. Studies distinguish between internal and external forms of constraints: internal constraints are primarily psychological and include factors such as limited knowledge and awareness, ignorance, egoism, or a lack of motivation; on the other hand, external constraints refer to structured obstacles, including high costs, inadequate availability, distance, or insufficient labelling and information (Humagain & Singleton, 2021).

For tourists to fully engage in ethical tourism, they must overcome a variety of constraints. The persistence of these barriers highlights the urgent need to evaluate those factors preventing consumers from putting its ethical intentions into behaviour. Addressing these issues not only clarifies the constraints faced by tourists but also helps to explain the discrepancy between tourist's intentions and their actual behaviour (Seyfi et al., 2024).

2.4.1 Theory of Constraints

This study utilizes the Theory of Constraints (TOC) as a guiding framework to analyse the barriers that Gen Z face when attempting to practice ethical tourism. According to Rahman (1998), TOC can be explained through two fundamental factors: first, that every system possesses at least one constraint, and second, that such constraints represent opportunities for improvement. In this sense, the presence of a constraint is not necessarily negative, but rather, viewed as an opportunity to evolve and strengthen the system. In the context of ethical tourism, the TOC framework helps identify the limits Gen Z face in pursuing ethical travel and, in doing so, develop a clearer path toward achieving ethical tourism.

The Theory of Constraints distinguishes three primary dimensions of barriers: intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural constraints. Intrapersonal constraints are rooted in the individual's internal psychological factors, such as personal beliefs, values, attitudes, and skills, which shape preferences and decision-making (Humagain & Singleton, 2021). These constraints are dynamic and subject to change depending on contextual or environmental influences. Interpersonal constraints, on the contrary, derive from social factors that influence individual choices. These include societal norms, peer pressure, and expectations that emerge from social interactions. They often change according to life-cycle stage, marital status, or the type of activity pursued (Aziz et al., 2022). Structural constraints, meanwhile, are external conditions beyond the individual's control that directly restrict participation. These include factors such as cost, time, availability of resources, accessibility, weather, and information (Rahman, 1998). Previous studies suggest that these constraints interact dynamically across levels, but they are typically experienced hierarchically, with intrapersonal constraint being the most immediate and structural constraints the most distant (Crawford & Stodolska, 2008). Additionally, Seyfi et al. (2024) found in its study that intrapersonal constraints are often linked with cognitive dissonance, risk aversion, and consumption inertia; interpersonal constraints are associated with green stigma, family dynamics, and social comparison; finally, structural constraints are related to limited accessibility and financial restrictions.

This framework is particularly suitable for this research as it provides a structured and systematic platform to examine the constraints faced by Gen Z at NHL Stenden when practicing ethical tourism. It does not only enable the categorization and deeper understanding of these barriers but also highlights their complexity.

2.5. Indicator matrix

All indicators from the intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structured constraints are summarised in the table below. This overview serves as a reference for writing the interview questions and guiding the interview process, as the indicators present potential responses related to the research questions. Accordingly, these indicators will be also included into the research matrix.

Table 1: Indicator Matrix

Intrapersonal Constraints		
Cognitive-Moral factors	Other issues have greater importance	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014)
	Expressing no alternative to current behaviours	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014)
	Using escape and relaxation as an excuse for ignoring environmental considerations	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014)
	Justifying non-sustainable behaviour while travelling	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014)
	Denying responsibility	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014)
	Claiming that personal behaviour has little impact	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014)
	Internal conflicts, reluctance to take risks, and resistance to changing consumption behaviour	Seyfi et al. (2024)
Motivational-Behaviour Factors	Being too occupied to change behaviours	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014)
	Lack of motivation	Humagain & Singleton (2021)
	Egoism	Humagain & Singleton (2021)
	Convenience preferences	Minazzi & Grechi (2025)
	Compensating unethical behaviour through perceived benefits of tourism	Minazzi & Grechi (2025)
Informational awareness	Limited knowledge and awareness	Humagain & Singleton (2021)
	Ignorance	Humagain & Singleton (2021)
Interpersonal Constraints		
Social-Normative Factors	Tendency to shift responsibility onto others	Pulido-Fernández et al. (2024); Juvan & Dolnicar (2014)
	Societal norms, peer pressure, and expectations from social interactions	Aziz et al. (2022); Minazzi & Grechi (2025)
	Family expectations, social stigma toward ethical behaviour, and the tendency to compare one's travel choices	Seyfi et al. (2024)
Structural Constraints		
Informational and Access Barriers	Not being correctly informed about ethical vacation alternatives	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014); Humagain & Singleton (2021)
	Insufficient labelling and information	Humagain & Singleton (2021); Rahman (1998)
	Inadequate availability of ethical tourism options	Humagain & Singleton (2021); Rahman (1998)
Economic and Practical Barriers	Financial limitations	Konieczna & Trybuś-Borowiecka (2025)
	High costs and expensive tourism services	Humagain & Singleton (2021); Rahman (1998); Minazzi & Grechi (2025)

	Time pressures	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014); Rahman (1998)
	Distance and accessibility barriers	Humagain & Singleton (2021); Rahman (1998)
Economic-Ideological Factors	Highlighting industries benefits from carbon-emitting options	Juvan & Dolnicar (2014); Seyfi et al. (2024)
	External environmental conditions (e.g., weather, infrastructure)	Rahman (1998)
	Limited accessibility and financial restrictions	Seyfi et al. (2024)

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1. Introduction of Methodology

In the methodology of this research, the research approach is presented with the purpose of leading a response to the problem statement. The chapter firstly starts with proposing a conceptual model designed based on the literature review presented above. Followed by three research questions, the research strategy and method, and the population and sampling. Additionally, the data analysis approach is described prior to the validity and reliability at section 3.5.1. To finalize the methodology, the limitations encountered in this research are found at the end of the chapter.

3.2. Conceptual Model

In this section, the conceptual framework developed in relation with the research questions, is presented and discussed. A conceptual framework serves as a visual representation of the relationships between significant concepts of the research (Ravitch et al., 2021). In the context of this research, the conceptual framework includes the main ideas examined in the Literature Review (Chapter 2) and shows how these concepts together explain the constraints influencing Gen Z at NHL Stenden in ethical tourism.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

The framework presented above connects intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural constraints, each one representing a dimension of constraints that influences the transformation of ethical intention into actual behaviour. These constraints are necessarily interconnected since individual (intrapersonal), social (interpersonal), and external (structural) factors collectively contribute to the limitations experienced by Gen Z at NHL Stenden in ethical tourism.

Each dimension of constraints encapsulates specific factors identified through the literature review. Intrapersonal constraints are the psychological and motivational barriers preventing individuals from engaging in ethical tourism, specifically cognitive-moral, motivational-behavioural, and information awareness factors. Interpersonal constraints relate to the social dynamics that influence ethical travel behaviour, such as social comparison or even green stigma. Finally, structural constraints are the external barriers beyond the individual's control. This constraint is divided into three factors: informational and access, economic and practical, and economic-ideological barriers.

The arrows connecting the different dimensions of constraints are used to present the interdependence among them. For instance, intrapersonal constraints may be reinforced by external barriers (structural constraints), and vice-versa. Understanding these interconnections, helps to respond to why Gen Z at NHL Stenden often struggle to translate their ethical intentions into ethical tourism behaviours.

3.3. Research questions

According to the literature review and the conceptual model presented above, three research questions were developed. These research questions are designed to support the problem statement: *“What are the constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?”*.

1. What are the **intrapersonal constraints** Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?
2. What are the **interpersonal constraints** Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?
3. What are the **structural constraints** Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?

Addressing each research questions provide a complete understanding of the constraints faced by Gen Z at NHL Stenden, as these dimensions are primarily interconnected. This chapter's continuation will present the methods used to answer the research questions.

3.4. Research Strategy and Research Method

The paragraphs below will present the methods in which the research questions were answered. In the first instance, the research approach of this dissertation is discussed, as well as the data collection methods, including the interview structure. A population and sampling chapter follows immediately after, together with the data analysis approach, validity, reliability, and finally, limitations.

3.4.1. Research Approach

For the purpose of this dissertation, a qualitative research approach was utilized. According to Teherani et al. (2015), qualitative research positions the researcher as the primary instrument of data collection, aiming to understand why events occur, how they unfold, and what it means to the participants studied. This approach provided an opportunity to examine how individuals experience and behave within a specific context. Therefore, by adopting a qualitative research approach, this dissertation aims to understand the experiences, meanings, and outcomes of practicing ethical tourism from the perspective of Gen Z at NHL Stenden.

A qualitative research approach highlights several key principles in research. Firstly, it comprehends the importance of allowing participants to express themselves in their own format during interviews. Secondly, it studies real-world experiences rather than controlled experimental environments. Thirdly, it argues that important data are often lost in quantification. Lastly, it explains that quantitative research neglects the context-sensitive nature of social life (Hammersley, 2013).

The constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden encounters in ethical tourism represents a relatively unexplored area, as existing studies often tend to not focus on if the intention turned into actual behaviour, limiting the possibility to identify potential constraints (Goncalves, 2013). For this reason, a qualitative approach was required to help discover and understand rather than simply measure or test something specific. The flexibility of qualitative research promoted a suitable approach for uncovering student's experiences, attitudes, and barriers towards ethical tourism. Namely, the dissertation was continuously adapted as new ideas and themes appeared from the data collected. Consequently, small sample sizes were preferred in this qualitative research for the aim of obtaining detailed and in-depth insights (Crouch & McKenzie, 2006).

Accordingly, as the justification above suggests, a qualitative approach represented the most appropriated method since it provided a platform for participants to fully share their personal experiences in their own words, allowing for detailed insights into different perspectives.

3.4.2. Data collection method

Data collection methods in qualitative research includes several formats, such as interviews, observations, document analysis, and focus groups (Busetto et al., 2020). Considering the research problem, objectives, and research questions of this research, it was essential to conduct in-depth interviews, as they allow for open-ended conversations and enable the exploration of specific issues beyond the limitations of pre-structured survey questions. Additionally, interviews of this nature are typically characterized for its duration time, taking minimum of half an hour per interview. For this dissertation, it was intended that the most suitable duration of the in-depth interviews was set to be approximately one-hour to ensure that all topics were thoroughly discussed. Respectively, some interviews had the duration of one-hour and thirty minutes.

This research focuses on three main themes: intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural constraints. Besides the limited number of topics of this research, it was essential that each theme was thoroughly examined to effectively address the purpose of this dissertation. Additionally, the usage of an in-depth interview was not only to gather detailed information but also to obtain different perspectives from different participants. This approach allowed each interviewee to share a unique “story”, which is only achievable through an in-depth interview method.

3.4.3. Population and Sampling

The population chosen for this dissertation consisted of Gen Z students participating in Tourism Management studies at NHL Stenden. In this research, a combination of purposive and convenience sampling was employed for participant selection. Palinkas et al. (2013) describes purposive sampling strategy as a technique that identifies and selects individuals or groups that have knowledge about a specific phenomenon. Translated into this research, tourism students learn various considerations of tourism, including ethical tourism. These students know what ethical tourism is, what it takes to achieve ethical tourism, and even themselves might have a different knowledgeable insight of what is preventing them from practicing in it. On the other

hand, convenience sampling is the data collection process from a research population that is easily accessible to the researcher (Golzar et al., 2022). In this case, the researcher had close contact with Gen Z individual's studying tourism management at NHL Stenden, which facilitated the reachability to this population sampling.

Data saturation occurs when sufficient information has been collected to allow an understanding of the research topic, minimizing the chances of new themes to emerge (Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006). However, data saturation was reached after eleven interviews, concluding that it was not necessary any further investigation. Interviews were conducted by contacting directly Gen Z students at NHL Stenden, expected to be held six interviews in person and three online, through Teams Meeting, during the month of November 2025. Additionally, all interviews were recorded with the consent of the participants to fully assure all information was taken to consideration and prevent misconceptions, as well as to be fully present during interviews.

3.5. Data analysis approach

After the data collection interviews were completed, the gathered data was analysed. In qualitative research, data are named, categorized, sorted and connected during the analysis phase. This process is realized through coding. Klapwijk (2011) describes coding as a tool to organize all the data collected and interpreting qualitative data, which is carried out in three stages: open, axial, and selective coding.

The first step, open coding, involved identifying and categorizing concepts and themes that emerged from the interviews into broad thematic domains, grouping together data that addressed similar topics. The second stage was axial coding, which focused on identifying relationships between open codes to create core categories. During axial coding, new concepts were developed while both key and minor themes were analysed comparatively. The final stage, selective coding, was applied to comply the data collected into the themes already identified by the literature review (Williams & Moser, 2018).

3.5.1. Validity and Reliability

In academic research, the credibility and trustworthiness of the research findings are determined through the concepts of validity and reliability (William, 2024). Validity refers to what extend the research measures or assesses the specific concept that the researcher aims

to measure (Karnia, 2024). On the other hand, reliability assesses the stability, consistency, and dependability of the research findings (Mira & Kofi, 2002).

The validity of this dissertation was ensured through multiple key factors. Firstly, a research matrix (Appendix A) was applied for the purpose of guaranteeing that all interview questions fully aligned with what the research aims to explore. Secondly, a semi-structured interview format helped to orientate the participant's responses towards the concepts of interest of this dissertation. Finally, pilot interviews were conducted to test the script clarity and finding possible missing concepts. With the application of all the above aspects, the research can be assured of validity.

In reality, three pilot interviews were conducted prior starting the main interview process. The first pilot interview revealed that multiple of the original questions of the semi-structured were rather too direct (Appendix C), leading to clear responses, but also to answers that appeared predetermined rather than a genuinely perspective. Following an analysis of this initial pilot, the interview script was revised for the purpose of asking participants to fully and freely share their authentic experiences while addressing the constraints experienced by Generation Z when engaging in ethical tourism (Appendix D). This adapted script was then used for the second trial interview, which concluded that the previous changes on the semi-structured questions were a success. However, the interview did not fully capture all the themes required for the objectives of this dissertation. Consequently, further modifications were made to the interview guide (Appendix E), which included an additional fifteen-minute workshop to the interview questions, strengthening the exploration of the three types of constraints identified in the literature review. The workshop consisted in three main exercises, each responding to one of the main constraint's themes. The instructions for this workshop can be found in Appendix B. Following these adjustments, a third pilot interview was conducted, resulting in obtaining rich and comprehensive data for this dissertation, and ensuring an appropriated interview structure.

Additionally, the reliability of this research was ensured through a transparent and consistent research process. Firstly, it was clearly explained how all the participants were chosen in chapter 3.4.3. allowing future studies to replicate the sampling methods. Secondly, all participants were interviewed under the same structure and set of questions, ensuring consistency throughout all the interviews. The interview scripts are included in the appendices G to enhance transparency of the data collected during interviews. Finally, the coding process is explained in section 3.5. and presented in appendix F, illustrating exactly how the data was analysed.

3.5.2. Limitations

For the full transparency of this dissertation, it is important to acknowledge potential limitations of the research. According to Ross and Zaidi (2019), limitations in research are the weakness within a research design that might influence the findings and conclusions.

Firstly, the dissertation is focusing its findings on a specific sample group, in which the interviewees are within the same generation, same area of study, and same university. This sample approach might lead to different responses on other possible studies that use a different sample group. Secondly, this dissertation uses a qualitative approach, which signifies that all data collected is fully dependent on the interpretation of the interviewer and interviewee. Therefore, how questions are made and how they are interpreted, is fully dependent on the participants (including the researcher) of this research, possibly leading to biases. Finally, the research is focusing on Gen Z tourism students, for their knowledge on ethical tourism. However, their level of ethical intention in participating in ethical options might differ, revealing different complexity and in-depth responses from the participants. During the data collection process, is deliberately exposed the different levels of ethical tourism intention's that each participant appears to engage in.

Therefore, for the full honesty and transference of this dissertation, the limitations discussed above are crucial to be shown, as it supports credibility and validity of the research, as well as, helping readers to interpret the findings more accurately.

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1. Introduction of Findings

This chapter focuses on presenting and analysing the findings that emerged from the interviews conducted with Gen Z tourism students at NHL Stenden. Its purpose is to address the dissertation's problem statement: "What are the constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?".

The identified constraints are categorized into three main types: Intrapersonal, Interpersonal, and Structural factors. Each category is examined through a corresponding research question in the following subchapters. All findings are based on a detailed coding process guided by key indicators from the literature review, ensuring alignment between the theoretical framework and the results. The full interview transcripts and coding process are provided in Appendices F and G.

4.2. Intrapersonal Constraints

This chapter focuses on the intrapersonal constraints identified throughout interviews. Additionally, it aims to respond to the research questions: "*What are the **intrapersonal constraints** Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?*".

The literature previously outlined key indicators that guided the data-collection process. These indicators were later connected to the interview findings, specifically within three categories, such as Cognitive-Moral factors, Motivational-Behavioural Factors, and Information-Awareness Factors. Each of these factors will be examined in the following sections in order to answer the research question and, ultimately, contribute to address the problem statement.

4.2.1. Cognitive-Moral factors

As Rogers and Breakey (2023) explored, cognitive-moral factors refer to the psychological processes individuals engage in when confronted with an ethical issue. These factors encompass the moral judgements, justifications, and internal reasoning that influence an individual's decision-making. Throughout the data collection process, many factors emerged as participants were questioned about their own experiences and explained how and why they reacted to the specific ethical concern. The following section analyses these responses.

Other issues have greater importance

Throughout interviews, it became evident that participants hold a set of priorities that they put forefront of ethical considerations while travelling, suggesting that individual preferences often outweigh ethical standards. For example, Participant 8 reflected that *“we had a bit more focus on what we actually wanted to do rather than actually considering more ethical practices, I think.”*, while Participant 3 stated that *“the ethical concerns would be the last of my priorities”*.

Many participants emphasized the importance of fun and enjoyment in their travels, as Participant 5 remarked, *“Tourists travel to have fun and enjoy”*, and Participant 7 further admitted *“I prefer that I am not ethical one time and enjoyed it, rather than just not go because I want to be ethical”*. This sentiment was further summarized in Participant’s 5 mindset of *“I want to get what I paid for”*, highlighting a focus on fulfilling personal expectations over ethical intentions.

Comfort and convenience were also frequently cited as a main constraint to not participant in ethical travel. Participant 3 explained *“Because comfort and affordability are a priority for me while travelling, and I feel like convenience is a synonym to like affordability and comfort. it's just what I'm seeking for when I go on holiday somewhere.”* Similarly, Participant 6 noted difficulty in ethical decision-making, stating *“It’s just much easier to plan something if you don’t consider the ethical aspects”*.

A final important remark concerned obligations, such as work requirements and family commitments. These obligations were often described as necessary and unavoidable, as Participant 7 mentioned *“I could not go, but it was a family vacation, and necessary”*, even if they conflicted with their ethical preferences *“I’m obligated to do something, I just do it because there are other priorities and sometimes you cannot just put your principles to the forefront.”* (Participant 4).

Expressing no alternative to current behaviours

Many participants also justified their actions by claiming no other alternatives available to behave ethically while travelling. This often was explained in relation to transportation methods, with Participant 9 stating *“there is not really an ethical way to get there”*, and Participant 7 similarly noted that *“there’s no other way to go”*. Also, Participant 4 extended this constraint beyond transportation, by explaining that *“if you go to a really popular museum, it will be*

crowded. And I cannot control the opening hours”, highlighting that certain aspects of travel are perceived as beyond their control.

Using escape and relaxation as an excuse for ignoring environmental considerations

Participants described travel as a way of relaxation and escape from everyday life, yet ethical travel was often associated as conflicting with this sense of relaxation, as Participant 10 noted *“you just make an unethical decision just because you want more relaxation”*, understanding that participants cannot engage in both simultaneously. Additionally, Participant 9 illustrated a desire to escape everyday issues, including ethical concerns, when stated *“I want to switch off my brain, but I do it because I'm trying to get away and have just a relaxing holiday”*.

Participants also rationalised unethical behaviour by highlighting the limited duration and frequency of their holidays. For instance, Participant 8 explained *“it was my only vacation, so I thought that it would be fine if this time we didn't act ethically”*, and further added, *“I only had one week and wanted to make the most of the vacation”*. This reflects a participant's belief that short-term holidays justify overlooking the consequences of unethical travel behaviour.

Justifying non-sustainable behaviour while travelling

When participants were questioned about their travel behaviours, many provided clear justifications for choosing the unethical option. A common response was that behaving ethically in their everyday life, gave them an opportunity to lower their ethical standards while travelling. For example, Participant 3 explained *“Because also I feel when you're at home, you're also trying to be ethical and you're behaving well, I guess, because you're not taking any airplanes or anything. So then that one time where you actually take an airplane and everything, then you're like, okay, now I make an exception”*. This statement indicates that participants viewed holidays as a temporarily suspension of their ethical obligations, without sensing guilt.

Another common justification during interviews was framing their behaviours as a form of morally compensation, as Participant 5 explained this logic by stating *“also I think if I go or not go, the animal is still going to be there and it's still, maybe it's not driving me, but it's driving another tourist so maybe I will give him like €5 more so he can give the animal more to drink or something and then in my case, it would be OK in my mind.”*.

Other participants conform their behaviour with their surroundings. For example, Participant 6 claims *“I feel like if more people do it, then I feel it's not that bad of a thing to do”*, indicating that

if other people are doing it, it reduced their sense of responsibility for acting unethically. Also, during interviews, participants stated that since some unethical practices already exist, they should not feel guilty for participating in them, as Participant 11 justifies *“is it bad for environment? Yes. Is it already there? Then use it.”*, while Participant 7 noted that *“other people were going to, so at least I could enjoy something that I really wanted to do, if it is going to be done either way”*.

Finally, Participant 8 emphasized that each individual has its personal limits regarding ethical behaviour, and the ethical behaviour should not cause personal cost: *“It's more polluting and less ethical environmentally wise, but it also takes a toll on your body if you're not used to it.”*

Denying responsibility

Another factor of intrapersonal constraints encountered during interviews was the tendency of participants to not acknowledge personal responsibility. This aspect appeared similarly in different ways during participant's interviews, however the statements below were coded under “denying responsibility” since participants shifted accountability from their own actions rather than attempting to justify unethical behaviour.

Participant 2 stated *“Because is only this time, it would be different if I would do it every time, you know?”*. In this quote, the participant did not acknowledge its behaviour since it had the belief that isolated unethical behaviour does not contribute to meaningful harm.

Furthermore, participants also explained that their behaviour is a translation of stakeholder's behaviour such as the government and the tourism industry. For example, Participant 3 argued *“it's not really, I think, the consumer's fault, but more of the government and the people who are offering it”*, positioning the responsibility into those who create and regulate tourism products, rather on themselves. Additionally, participant 4 reinforced this idea by stating *“it shouldn't be one person's effort”*, translating that the responsibility does not rely on only one person, but on a collective group.

For some participants, obligations were described as a constraint, as they felt limited in their own ability to practice ethical tourism. For example, Participant 1 clearly shared *“Work wise I have to because you know it's work”*, while Participant 2 included *“I wouldn't have the flexibility of choosing someplace closer.”*

Claiming that personal behaviour has little impact

A prominent factor that emerged from interviews was to what extent participants felt that their individual action had an influence, as Participant 4 noted *“individual actions can make a difference, but I’m sceptical about how huge the impact is.”* This is a crucial constraint since participants stopped to feel empowered and therefore, stopped to participate in ethical tourism. Additionally, Participant 10 illustrated this clearly, stating *“if I don't do it, it's not going to change anything so it's not going to make a big difference”*.

Other participants explained that individual actions have to be accompanied by a collective effort, either for being meaningful or to feel motivated in maintaining their ethical behaviour. For example, Participant 4 explained *“when it comes to turning it into a collective effort, it's really limited. Because I don't feel that much powerful in this sense”*, highlighting that individual behaviour needs to be supported by a collective effort. This sentiment was shared with Participant 7, who questioned *“the problem is that, not everyone is choosing the responsible action, so why should I do it, and not do things that I want to do, if other people can?”*, as well as Participant 8 *“I believe that many people disregard these aspects because they say that nobody cares or why do I have to do it if the others don't?”*. These statements reinforced that the problem is not individual action, but rather in sustaining them when others are seen as not contributing.

Conversely, some participants felt that their individual action were irrelevant since some situations were unchangeable. Participant 9 expressed *“it's kind of impossible because it's already an Airbnb so it's not going to change.”* and added *“it would be more ethical to leave houses for families, but I can't really change that.”*. These responses illustrated the sentiment of little impact of individual actions in ethical tourism.

Internal conflicts, reluctance to take risks, and resistance to changing consumption behaviour

During interviews, participants revealed internal psychological barriers that prevented them from practicing ethical tourism. One of the barriers found was the internal conflict between wanting to act ethically while wanting to pursue personal needs. For example, Participant 10 stated this tension clearly, saying *“conflict with yourself because you know that is not ethical for you to do, but you would love to do it.”*. On the same view, Participant 5 explained *“I want to be respectful and ethical and not the typical mass tourist, but I also paid to go to this place”*. These statements illustrate a conflict since participants recognized the ethical choice but prioritized their own preferences.

A second topic that emerged frequently from the data collection process was the uncertainty of what was the most ethical action. Many participants described situations where they felt unsure of what was the best ethical alternative, since both perspectives would implicate unethical matters, as Participant 5 expressed *“either way, I’m kind of doing something wrong”*. This feeling frequently emerged from different ethical norms across cultures and individuals. For example, Participant 8 explained *“Maybe someone’s beliefs are different than mine because of their culture, and if we want to say also religion”*, while Participant 7 reflected that *“what I think is ethical might be different from you”*.

Additionally, some participants acknowledged the dilemma between being loyal to their personal ethical values or adapting to local expectations. Participant 2 expressed this tension *“sometimes is quite difficult to understand if you should adapt to their ethical values, because if you go against them, you are being truthful to your ethical concerns”*. This constraint, ultimately, discouraged ethical behaviour, as the same participant commented *“I think there were times where I had the intention to act ethically, but honestly I did not know if it would be worse if I actually acted on it.”*

Finally, the interviews revealed reluctance to change familiar routines while travelling, as Participant 4 clearly stated that *“I don’t think it’s enough to change my behaviour completely”*, while Participant 1 explained *“Just simply sticking to the daily basis and ensuring that I do them when I travel because it’s just how I am and how I operate”*. The participants also shown that this resistance is often associated with inconvenience or lack of motivation in ethical tourism, as Participant 3 admitted *“it’s going too much out of what I am willing to do.”*, which Participant 5 summarized *“it’s really hard to be consistent in ethical tourism”*.

4.2.2. Motivational-Behaviour Factors

Motivation-behaviour factors refer to the individual’s daily patterns, as well as the willingness and motivation that shape their participation in ethical tourism (Tang et al., 2022). These factors come as a step forward in understanding the intrapersonal constraints in this research, since is focusing on the individual’s inclination to engage in ethical tourism, rather than analysing the moral values, as it was done in the section prior.

Being too occupied to change behaviours

During interviews, participants were questioned about their experience with planning ethical travel, and many identified this stage as a significant barrier. Several participants explained that

planning an ethical travel is particularly time-consuming, as Participant 6 *“I think it does take more time, more effort to plan ethical options.”*. This was directly linked to participants perceived time constraints in such planning. For example, Participant 10 affirmed *“I don't have the time to just to do the right thing and just considering ethical options.”*, while Participant 9 added *“I am a student, I do not have time”*.

Lack of motivation

Lack of motivation emerged as a significant constraint among participants. During interviews, many participants admitted that ethical intentions was not a prevalent factor in their travels, either from not having the ethical intention at all or from not wanting to associate travel experiences with their ethical values. This can be seen in Participant 5 statement *“I don't think I had this intention, of ok, I'm not doing this, not doing that because of ethical reasons, only because we didn't feel like it”*, while Participant 10 said *“I didn't really think about being ethical in traveling itself”*.

Additionally, several participants also expressed lack of motivation to seek out ethical tourism options, even if aware of the existence of these options. For example, Participant 6 said *“I think we just went with it, I didn't check information before, it was just what we wanted to do”*. Interestingly, Participant 5 justified that their motivation in participating in ethical tourism was context-dependent: *“I actually prioritise ethical considerations, but not every time and not intentionally I think, depending on the situation.”*

Egoism

When discussed their travel decisions, many participants indicated to put their egoistic needs over ethical considerations. These constraints appeared to happen for many reasons. Some tourists openly acknowledged that, even when aware that a behaviour may be unethical, their desire to experience something they value personally, was bigger, as Participant 6 expressed *“I will probably still join, if I think it's something that I really would love to do, even if unethical.”*

A related pattern involved participant's egoistic reasoning in relation to the behaviour of other tourists. For example, Participant 9 remarked *“if I don't go, people are still going to go, and I will be missing out. So, I prefer to go, even if that is not the best option.”*, while Participant 2 similarly stated *“I prefer to get my chance of seeing it, even if it is unethical, rather than giving that spot to someone else”*. These statements illustrate a self-focused mindset, in which participants emphasized their personal needs when those were not meet by others.

Distance and less opportunities were also a frequent factor. Participants often described ethical behaviour as less important when they were visiting distant destinations. For instance, Participant 1 explained *“if I would be somewhere only for a day and I don't have a chance to come back, then in that case, I would probably stay if it's something I want to see or want to experience.”*, which Participant 2 added *“And if I really want to go to, then I don't choose to go somewhere closer because it's ethically better.”*

Finally, as tourism students, several interviews linked ethical behaviour to potential negative impacts on their future careers. For example, Participant 7 claimed *“If people stop travelling because they don't want to participate in overtourism and unethical behaviours, then I am not going to have a job.”*, while Participant 2 further reinforced this statement *“I won't prejudicated myself for that”*.

Convenience preferences

Participants consistently identified convenience preferences as one of the most significant intrapersonal constraints. Many participants confirmed that if the ethical option was not of convenience for their travel experience, then they would likely overlook it, as Participant 2 exclaimed *“convenience weighs heavier for me than ethics”*.

This convenience preferences were manifested in different ways throughout interviews. Many participants related convenience with time efficiency. For example, Participant 3 affirmed *“I feel we just choose whatever is quicker”*, reinforced by Participant 6 statement *“I don't want to spend hours on looking for something that I want to go do”*. On the other hand, participants associated this aspect with financial convenience. For example, Participant 7 affirmed *“it's more expensive and it takes more time and I'm less comfortable, I will obviously pick the other option, even if it is less ethical.”*

Finally, participants often prioritized practical needs and personal preferences over ethical considerations. Participant 2 said *“I have people that I want to visit, and they happen to live there, so I put my preferences first”*, while Participant 7 affirmed *“we just book it conforming our preferences, if it is an ethical option great, if it is regular, then that's fine too.”* Participant 4 summarized this mindset effectively: *“I prefer to have an easier trip rather than everything being 100% ethical”*.

Compensating unethical behaviour through perceived benefits of tourism

When discussed the consequences of unethical tourism, most participants admitted being a complex topic. Participants, such as Participant 2 for example, affirmed *“overtourism may harm the local community, but it also brings benefits to it, in the sense of creating jobs and people actually being able to finance their own lives.”*. This perfectly illustrates how some participants recognized the harmful impact of unethical tourism but perceived the beneficial outcomes as outweighing the negative consequences.

Most of the beneficial outcomes were centred on economic development, particularly in job creation within local communities. For example, Participant 11 highlighted *“When you look at Bali, for example, half of the economy is depending on tourism. It creates jobs, it creates knowledge, it also creates money.”*. Based on participants responses, this constraint is also what maintains many destinations alive, for example from Participant 3 response *“I feel that tourism it definitely is what maintains the island alive.”*.

As a result, many participants felt that their unethical behaviour was actually a beneficial consequence for many destinations and therefore complicated their motivation to behave ethically. For instance, Participant 7 expressed *“I would prefer to act unethical while travelling if that means that I am helping someone keep the job”*.

4.2.3. Information-Awareness Factors

In contrast to the previously discussed intrapersonal factors, Information-Awareness relate to how an individual's level of awareness and information significantly impacts their input in ethical tourism. As Aman et al. (2021) explains, ethical awareness is the first step of getting tourists to change their behaviours towards a more ethical option and therefore, crucial in shaping ethical behaviour. This section presents the data collected during interviews related to participant's awareness, knowledge and ignorance in ethical tourism practices.

Limited knowledge and awareness

During conversations, participants frequently admitted lack of awareness and information regarding ethical tourism, as Participant 8 stated *“I didn't have much awareness about ethical tourism and activities”*. Many interviewees expressed that they did not feel knowledgeable enough to participate in or promote ethical travel practices. For example, Participant 2 reflected *“I feel if I would be having a solid knowledge that it is for sure harming the environment, I wouldn't feel uncomfortable speaking about it”*, while Participant 7 similarly explained *“if I am*

uninformed then I have no knowledge behind my travel decisions.”. This lack of information often led to uncertainty when attempted to participate in ethical tourism, as Participant 8 explained *“I think the doubt comes when I am not informed enough on the topic”*.

Participants also highlighted that insufficient awareness sometimes led them to unintentionally engage in unethical behaviours. For example, Participant 5 admitted *“was not aware that I was being part of something that for me, is not correct to do with animals.”*, as well as Participant 8 reflected *“Looking back maybe I should have researched a bit more about it and about its ethical side of this experience.”*. Both of these statements demonstrate how lack of awareness and information resulted in unintentional participation in unethical tourism.

Additionally, participants recognized that a gap between ethical intentions and behaviour was likely to occur, but awareness and being correctly informed could reduce this discrepancy. Participant 4 explained *“you will end up having a gap but the size of the gap, it depends on how prepared you are or like how aware you are”*. Furthermore, participants recognized that without sufficient information, individual’s felt less capable of acting ethically, even when the behavioural change could be easily adopted. For example, Participant 6 noted *“also knowing more about it because some things I probably don’t even think about, that are easier to change than I think”*.

Ignorance

Ignorance emerged during interviews when participants revealed that, although they were aware of the unethical tourism behaviours, they still chose to ignore it. This factor appeared mostly connected to transportation methods, where participants felt that the unethical option was often the only feasible opportunity. For example, Participant 3 shared *“Because my dad has an apartment there, so we always stay there. So, it’s just easier to take two planes, even knowing that its wrong.”*, demonstrating ignorance towards ethical considerations if that promoted personal convenience. Similarly, Participant 6 stated *“I wanted to explore a new place, I wanted to meet my friend, and I wanted to be somewhere in the sun, so I still went knowing that it was wrong.”*, which shows overlooking unethical tourism in order to achieve personal desires.

Participants also noted that once they found themselves in an unethical situation, even if unintentionally, they often decided to remain in it, and ignore the unethical issues. For example, Participant 1 stated *“you just end up in some place which you didn’t intend to be, and it is super crowded. And, honestly, you might think that, oh actually that’s interesting so, let me stay here”*.

4.3. Interpersonal Constraints

This chapter focus on the interpersonal constraints identified during the interviews, and its purpose is to respond to the research question: “*What are the **interpersonal constraints** Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?*”.

Additionally, it will present an interpersonal factor that was derived from a connection of the key indicators identified in the literature review and the interview findings. This factor is named as Social-Normative. It is important to highlight that one of the practical constraints identified under the interpersonal factor, emerged during the coding of the interview data, consequently adding the Social Media Influence constraint. Although this theme was not anticipated in the literature review, it appeared consistently highlighted in participants responses, guaranteeing its identification as a new interpersonal constraint.

4.3.1. Social-Normative Factors

According to Saracevic and Schlegelmilch (2021) social-normative factors refer to the external social influences that shape an individual’s behaviour. These influences such as pressure, societal norms, or expectations from one’s social environment, affect individual’s ethical decision-making by encouraging individuals to act according to “what is commonly done”.

Tendency to shift responsibility onto others

Participants responded that it was common to shift responsibilities onto other people when discussing ethical tourism, as Participant 2 responded “*Yeah, I think we all shift responsibilities to other people.*”. Also, many participants believed that the blame did not lie within the individuals but rather on the social environment that was surrounding them. For example, Participant 5 admitted “*I think people excuse their bad behaviour conforming the amount of people that is doing them*” which directly aligned with Participant 1 statement “*It wasn’t fully on me what I did*”.

Societal norms, peer pressure, and expectations from social interactions

Participants consistently expressed that their ethical tourism behaviour was highly dependent on the social environment around them. Many described a tendency to mimic the behaviour of their surroundings and to conform to the values and norms present in that environment. For instance, Participant 2 shared “*I was also like looking at locals if they do it and if they did it then I did the same.*”, which was further highlighted with Participant 5 explanation “*People normally*

follow one another, so if tourists would behave ethically when travelling, I think everyone would start following that behaviour, like nobody would question it". These statements illustrate how societal norms and expectations often influenced individual's ethical behaviour.

Several participants also highlighted that travelling accompanied restricted their ethical behaviour, as group dynamics challenged personal decision-making. Participant 6 noted *"If it was in a group, and they were doing something, then I think I would probably ignore my ethical concerns and just do it"*, and Participant 1 reinforced this *"if I'm with someone else, I cannot only consider myself."* Peer pressure further intensified this feeling of conformity. Many participants expressed that when travelling in a group, they followed group decisions to avoid feeling isolated, as Participant 6 shared *"if I travel with friends, I don't want to do things on my own so I would always stick to with what they do"*, added that *"I would feel too awkward if I was the only one not doing it, even if I thought it was wrong."* Participant 6 was showing that individuals preferred to ignore their ethical values in order to fulfil the group expectations.

In addition, participants emphasized that those which they travel with, such as friends, family, and partner, influenced their ethical behaviour. Participant 1 stated *"friends and then equally parent's family because those are the people I travel with. So obviously they are a big influence"*, while Participant 7 responded *"if my partner nags me about it continuously, then I will most likely go"*.

Family expectations, social stigma toward ethical behaviour, and the tendency to compare one's travel choices

Participants felt that family dynamics strongly influenced their ethical travel decisions, as they explained that when travelling with family, they had limited autonomy to act according to their ethical values. For example, Participant 5 stated that when travelling, *"it's always what the parents decide, so I do not have much choice"*, which was reinforced when Participant 5 added *"with family, it's really hard to do your own stuff and they're not willing to understand"*.

Another factor found during interviews, was the presence of social stigma towards ethical behaviour. Some participants included that the society does not always support or validate ethical travel choices and may even judge those who practice it. Participant 5 explained *"nobody wants to believe you that you only didn't go because of that; they will say that it was because you did not have time or something. So, in that case, you're it's kind of like a must."* This statement shows a societal pressure to conform to the "normal" travel, which discouraged

students to act ethically, as is possible to notice from the same participant *“I actually do feel that I would be judged”*.

Social media influence

During interviews, participants consistently expressed social media influence on their travel choices, often affecting the ethical considerations involved. Several participants acknowledged that their travel planning was based on social media research, as Participant 9 stated *“I think nowadays social media influences it a lot more of where I want to go”*, let to a compromise on individuals’ ethical grounds *“if you just plan your trips according to the standards of your influencers then you have to give up on some ethical considerations in a way”* (Participant 4).

A key constraint found was the global share of the same destination or activity across social media platforms, contributing to overcrowding. For example, Participant 9 said *“Because of social media, the same post that I saw, and my friends saw that made us go there, other people saw it too, and everyone wants to go there which makes it overcrowded and unethical”*. Many participants noted that social media often only presents the positive side of an experience, which created misleading impressions on participants, as Participant 8 shared *“Also because with the social media today, we most of the time we only see one of the sides of the situation and you don't see the other one”*.

Furthermore, participants recognized that social media itself was used as a way of following societal standards. Individuals described a pressure to replicate experiences they saw online and to share those same experiences publicly to maintain a sense of belonging. Participant 7 shared *“if people have the opportunity to go do something that others did or posted online, they are going to do it, because we always want to compare each other to others”*, followed by the statement of Participant 5 *“you think everyone needs to know what you're doing at every moment”*.

Influencer’s culture was also present in the travel behaviour of participants. Many explained that influencers engage in extreme actions (often unethical) to differentiate their content from others, which consequently influences followers. For example, Participant 5 claimed *“I also think because of that a lot of influencers, they want to find something new and they maybe, I don't know, go on top of like a very important touristic site where you usually are not allowed to film or something just because of clicks. And then you end up in the unethical part of social media when you travel.”*. Similarly, Participant 4 added *“If you just really want to do it because*

you are influenced by someone else then this is the dangerous part of social media in my opinion it can lead to something bad in terms of ethical considerations”.

4.4. Structural Constraints

This chapter aims to present the Structural Constraints identified throughout the interviews. Furthermore, it also has the purpose to respond to the research questions: *“What are the structural constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?”.*

In the literature review was highlighted core indicators for the purpose of directing the data-collection process. Further on the research, these same indicators were connected with the data collected from the interviews, which highlighted three primary categories, including Informational and Access Factors, Economic and Practical Factors, and Economic-Ideological Factors. Each factor will be analysed below in order to answer the research question and help to address the problem statement.

4.4.1. Informational and Access Factors

Gomes and Lopes (2023) highlighted how information strongly shape individuals’ engagement with ethical tourism. When travellers are adequately and correctly informed, they tend to feel more responsible about their behaviours, more capable of acting conforming their ethical intentions, and ultimately more likely to adopt ethical tourism practices. The following section presents the findings on how lack of information and access constrain individuals from acting ethically during their travels.

Not being correctly informed about ethical vacation alternatives

The interviews revealed a consistent barrier related to the information provided to participants. Participant 4 explained a lack of confidence in the information available, revealing that *“I don’t think that the information is enough or clear or honest”.* This aspect had several consequences, such as limiting participations’ motivation to engage in ethical tourism. For example, Participant 7 described feeling uncertainty about which alternative was genuinely ethically better: *“sometimes, there isn’t really a better alternative, because both are going to have their pros and cons”.* Such attitude often emerged from the perception of information biases, in which companies “mask” negative aspects of an unethical action, as Participant 4 responded *“when*

you check some places, especially online, you see only the positive aspects of them. No one shows you, oh yeah, it's crowded and it's like full of people or like animals are tortured”.

Insufficient labelling and information

Participants admitted feeling inadequately informed by tourism stakeholders, which reflected on their poor engagement in ethical practices. Specifically, many noted that, if the information was available, it was difficult to access, leaving individuals responsible for seeking themselves. For example, Participant 2 explained *“you've got to go find the information for yourself because it is not easily in front of you”*. This though was reinforced by the perception that companies prioritize promoting unethical options, as Participant 11 commented *“the information is not normally very easy to access for the ones that doesn't sell that often, that being the ethical options”*.

Another reason for participants to feel insufficient information was directly related to the industry itself, as Participant 2 said *“Companies should provide more information, that's for sure. But yeah, also like tourism students in that sense, then yes, schools should inform them better”*. Many participants acknowledged that while experiencing a tourism product, many of those organizations did not provide the information, often being the participants to ask for it. For example, Participant 10 reflected *“I feel like is just there, they don't really communicate those with a free will, let's say, you have to ask for it”*, while Participant 9 described *“With the tour guide there, he didn't really say that there were actions that we did that would be like unethical. We went to look at different places and went also like into some caves. But he never told us like, yeah, this is not ethical to do or like he never really talked about ethical things”*.

Interestingly, participants clearly emphasized this factor as a constraint, explaining that without this limitation, individuals would naturally increase their participation in ethical tourism, as Participant 2 shared *“if people had more information and more options about ethical choices, then is almost impossible that more tourists would not participate in that, simply because of you know, the higher you promote something, also the higher people will participate in it”*.

Inadequate availability of ethical tourism options

The data collected from interviews demonstrated how participants often felt lack of availability of ethical tourism options. Several participants explained that, even when they had ethical intentions, they were unable to act according to them because other ethical alternatives simply did not exist. For example, Participant 5 explained *“limited sustainable options available*

because sometimes even if you want to do it, you can't". Also, according to earlier findings, that accessibility was a crucial factor for engaging in ethical behaviour, many participants reported that higher availability would reduce the effort to look for information and consequently encourage participation in ethical tourism. Participant 6 stated this clearly: *"I think maybe if options would be there more and easier, then I wouldn't need more time to research them"*.

4.4.2. Economic and Practical Factors

This section has the aim of understand how financial and practical barriers influence participants behaviour towards ethical tourism. According to Lasisi et al. (2025), economic cost is typically indicated as a limiting factor on individual's motivation in engaging in ethical practices, while practical factors can be a breakpoint for individual's ethical decision-making. Below is going to be exposed the data collected from the interviews, and how economic and practical factors influenced participants in their tourism experiences.

Financial limitations

Financial limitations were one of the most significant constraints that participants indicated for not engaging in ethical tourism. Specifically, as the research group is Gen Z students, many participants explained that they had the ethical intention and would prefer to engage in ethical tourism however, due to financial limitations, that was not possible. For example, Participant 8 explained *"I know many people that would rather pick the ethical choice over the unethical one, but as you said It's also always the most expensive one and for us, we don't have a fixed income to sustain that"*.

Additionally, Participant 3 added *"the more affordable is always better for a student"* which directly aligned with Participant 5 saying *"as a student still there are some things that you are not willing to pay more"*. Both of these statements demonstrate how students were very restricted when trying to engage in ethical tourism, and that this constraint completely shaped the tourism experience of individuals, as Participant 9 described *"I would act more unethical because I don't have the money to act ethical"*.

Finally, participants also presented signs of frustration in relation to insufficient funds to support ethical practices. For example, Participant 5 responded *"if there are ethical options, if you do not have the money, then it's not even relevant that they are available. I would feel even worse if it were available and I just couldn't afford it"*.

High costs and expensive tourism services

The high costs of ethical tourism options were repeatedly criticised throughout interviews. Many participants claimed that practicing ethical tourism was an expensive activity that went beyond their financial capabilities, which led them to choose less ethical alternatives. For example, Participant 8 explained *“ethical options are basically inaccessible or very limited as a choice, because it is so expensive. So, you basically have to rely on the unethical choice or completely change your mind and forget about your travel plans”*. Participants also demonstrated a desire to engage in ethical tourism but expressed that the high cost of it, did not allowed it, as Participant 1 stated *“I know often for many people it's a case that they would love to do it, but then I cannot because the price of it”*.

Some participants even attributed responsibility towards this constraint, suggesting that it was not seen as “normal” within the tourism market because of the elevated costs. Participant 7 justified *“ethical options are always more expensive, that's a reason why it's not as normalised or popular than regular options”*, in which Participant 8 further concluded *“If it was more accessible, economically wise, I think more people would pick that choice”*. Therefore, it is possible to comprehend how participants justified selecting less ethical choices by accounting fault on the high cost of ethical tourism.

Finally, participants claimed feeling frustrated with this financial limitation, as it was shown by Participant 2 *“I'm annoyed that there is not a more affordable ethical option”*. Participant 1 further enhanced this emotion *“you want to act right but then you got to literally pay the price for it”*, demonstrating how high costs and expensive tourism services acted as a significant constraint for Gen Z individuals seeking to participate in ethical tourism.

Time pressures

Participants also indicated time pressures as a significant constraint when related ethical activities with too time-consuming. Participant 3 admitted *“if I have to do something that's going to take me double as long then I am not going to do it “*, further reinforcing *“if it's not too time consuming, it's also more likely to be chosen by not only students, but everyone”*. These reflections demonstrate how time pressures discouraged individuals from participating in ethical tourism. Also, Participant 8 shared an example in which the ethical option was not chosen because it required more time than the unethical alternative: *“we could have done the activities with the probably public transportation, but it would have taken us double the time to go”*.

Additionally, participants also reflected that shorter trips would influence their willingness to engage in ethical tourism options. For instance, Participant 5 commented *“I will do with a regular one because I'm not there for a long time.”*

Distance and accessibility barriers

Many participants acknowledged that engaging in ethical tourism practices was often related to the accessibility in which those options were provided. For example, Participant 10 explained *“I feel like also obviously accessibility makes it harder to practice ethical tourism”*, which was reinforced as a constraint with the Participant 5 statement *“if it is not easy to reach, then tourists just don't bother”*. These reflections highlight how individuals were more likely to choose ethical alternatives when they were easily reachable.

Participants also noted that some destinations simply did not offer the opportunities to participate in ethical tourism, as Participant 2 revealed *“I couldn't practice it as much as I would want to, or as easily I could do here in the Netherlands, let's say. So yeah, there I couldn't, even if I wanted to”*, while Participant 9 observed *“in some places it's difficult to be more ethical, if you are on holidays in some specific places”*.

Another constraint identified in interviews was the role of distance, which often forced participants to choose a less ethical behaviour. For example, Participant 8 said *“the last thing I want to do move around by car. But in that case, it was needed because of the type of trip we had planned”*.

4.4.3. Economic-Ideological Factors

This section directly relates to the relationship between participant's ideological intention and financial aspects. The factors highlight how economic restrictions from external parties, such as the tourism industry, destinations, and tourism organization, can limit individual's ethical intention (Li et al., 2023). In shorter words, how tourism stakeholders need to comply with ethical practices to the same extent that tourists are expected to.

Highlighting job creation benefits of carbon-emitting industries

According to participants, the tourism industry itself often prioritised profit over promoting ethical tourism, as Participant 4 stated *“The industry pushes entrepreneurs or companies to make money”*. Consequently, this signified a limitation for individuals who were trying to engage in ethical tourism practices, as information and options were not provided by those who

offer tourism experiences. Participant 8 explained *“the majority are big multinational companies, which and whose only purpose is to make money pretty much. And I believe that ethical tourism, ethical anything, and ethical choices, they don't sell or at least they don't sell as much as the unethical ones, probably”*, later emphasized with *“companies always have the purpose to sell you their products, so they're never going to say our product is not ethical”*.

External environmental conditions (e.g., weather, infrastructure)

Some participants indicated that ethical tourism options were not always guaranteed due to the infrastructures the country provided. For example, Participant 7 shared *“in Morocco they don't recycle, so I couldn't do anything about that”*, illustrating that the participant could not maintain its ethical values since the necessary infrastructures were not available.

Additionally, Participant 2 explained situations where the lack of infrastructure led to adopt the unethical option, because it was the only option available: *“the infrastructure generally is not so well developed, of course. And there's like trash everywhere. And I was so desperately looking for trash cans. And then like throwing away your trash just like the locals do on the ground. I mean, you have to do it too because if there are no other options”*.

Furthermore, both statements reveal that participants often interpreted these actions as acceptable (even if against their ethical values) because it aligned with local norms, and therefore, limited participants from engaging in ethical tourism.

Limited accessibility and financial restrictions

During interviews, participants explained that ethical tourism options were often more difficult to access compared to less ethical options. Participant 5 stated *“if you want to maybe decide to go to a place or visit a place that is more ethically, sometimes you have to actively choose it, in the sense that it is not easily accessible.”* This quote highlights how ethical tourism options were frequently harder to reach, demotivating individuals from participating in an ethical tourism.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

5.1. Introduction of Conclusion

This final chapter answers the problem statement: “What are the constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden face in ethical tourism?”, by synthesising the findings from the three research questions addressing intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural constraints. It also presents the adjusted indicator matrix as well as, discussing the study’s contributions, and providing recommendations for future research and practical implications for the tourism industry.

5.2. Problem Statement

This dissertation answers that Gen Z at NHL Stenden face intrapersonal, interpersonal, and structural constraints in ethical tourism.

At the intrapersonal level, personal priorities, moral compensations, and insufficient knowledge often outweigh ethical intentions in travel decision-making. Interpersonally, ethical tourism behaviour is limited by the social travel standards and group expectations. Structurally, financial constraints frequently lead students to compromise their ethical values.

Simply, Gen Z students at NHL Stenden do not lack ethical travel awareness, but are constrained by internal, social, and structural barriers that impeded ethical intentions to translate to actual behaviour.

5.3. Adjusted Indicator Matrix

Table 2: Adjusted Indicator Matrix

Intrapersonal Constraints	
Cognitive-Moral factors	Other issues have greater importance
	Expressing no alternative to current behaviours
	Using escape and relaxation as an excuse for ignoring environmental considerations
	Justifying non-sustainable behaviour while travelling
	Denying responsibility
	Claiming that personal behaviour has little impact
Motivational-Behaviour Factors	Internal conflicts, reluctance to take risks, and resistance to changing consumption behaviour
	Being too occupied to change behaviours
	Lack of motivation
	Egoism

	Convenience preferences
	Compensating unethical behaviour through perceived benefits of tourism
Informational awareness	Limited knowledge and awareness
	Ignorance
Interpersonal Constraints	
Social-Normative Factors	Tendency to shift responsibility onto others
	Societal norms, peer pressure, and expectations from social interactions
	Family expectations, social stigma toward ethical behaviour, and the tendency to compare one's travel choices
	Social Media Influences
Structural Constraints	
Informational and Access Barriers	Not being correctly informed about ethical vacation alternatives
	Insufficient labelling and information
	Inadequate availability of ethical tourism options
Economic and Practical Barriers	Financial limitations
	High costs and expensive tourism services
	Time pressures
	Distance and accessibility barriers
Economic-Ideological Factors	Highlighting industries benefits from carbon-emitting options
	External environmental conditions (e.g., weather, infrastructure)
	Limited accessibility and financial restrictions

5.4. Research Question 1

“WHAT ARE THE INTRAPERSONAL CONSTRAINTS GEN Z AT NHL STENDEN FACE IN ETHICAL TOURISM?”

To answer Research Question 1, the findings chapter allowed a clear understanding of the intrapersonal constraints affecting students, in which three main categories of constraints were analysed: cognitive-moral, motivational-behavioural, and informational awareness.

The first factor identified was Cognitive-Moral factors, where the interviews highlighted three constraints as particularly influential for students when practicing ethical tourism. Students often prioritized personal enjoyment, comfort, and convenience over ethical considerations, while adding obligations as “more important” than ethical practices. Also, unethical travel behaviour was commonly justified through moral rationalisations, including believing that everyday ethical actions compensate for unethical travel choices or normalizing unethical actions since they are largely accepted. Participants also experienced internal conflicts, such

as uncertainty about which option provoked the least harm, resistance to change familiar travel routines, and difficulty prioritizing ethical values.

The second factor identified was Motivational-Behavioural factors. Although participants acknowledged unethical behaviour, many preferred to still prioritize personal needs. Additionally, students felt less obligated to act ethically if other individuals did not, while some participants justified unethical actions due to future career expectations within the tourism industry. Finally, infrequent travel led participants to prioritise personal preferences and perceive tourism's positive impacts as outweighing the negative consequences of unethical tourism.

The final factor, Informational awareness, constrained ethical decision-making. Many participants reported insufficient knowledge to confidently choose ethical options, which contributed to unethical behaviour. Increased awareness was acknowledged as a key factor in reducing the attitude-behaviour gap.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that ethical tourism behaviour is primarily constrained by internal factors, as intrapersonal constraints limit individuals even before external influences are involved.

5.5. Research Question 2

“WHAT ARE THE INTERPERSONAL CONSTRAINTS GEN Z AT NHL STENDEN FACE IN ETHICAL TOURISM?”

To address Research Question 2, the findings indicate that interpersonal constraints strongly influence student's ethical tourism behaviour, specially through Social-Normative factors. Beyond the established indicators from the literature, Social Media Influence emerged from the interviews as a fundamental constraint for participants.

The influence of social media was identified as a major interpersonal barrier, as participants reported relying heavily on social media when planning their travels, often to align with societal travel standards. However, social media was perceived to present only the appealing side of destinations, hiding unethical practices and issues. This encourages imitation of popular travel experiences, contributing to overcrowding and unethical behaviour, both intentionally and unintentionally. Travel influencers were seen to intensify this effect by normalising and promoting unethical practices that participants felt pressured to follow.

Additionally, participants frequently adjusted their actions to match those of their travel companions, with group dynamics and peer pressure discouraging ethical actions. The avoidance of social exclusion often led participants to disregard their ethical values to meet group expectations.

Therefore, the findings demonstrate that interpersonal constraints highly shape ethical tourism behaviour, as students frequently prioritize social conformity over personal ethical values.

5.6. Research Question 3

“WHAT ARE THE STRUCTURAL CONSTRAINTS GEN Z AT NHL STENDEN FACE IN ETHICAL TOURISM?”

Regarding Research Question 3, the findings show that structural constraints significantly restrict student's engagement in ethical tourism, even when ethical intentions are present. Three main structural constraints were identified: informational and access, economic and practical, and economic-ideological factors.

To begin with, Informational and Access factors were emphasized as participants reported insufficient information and visibility of ethical tourism options, as tourism organizations tend to promote regular options rather than ethical alternatives. As a result, students felt forced to independently search for ethical options, which discouraged ethical engagement.

The second factor concerned Economic and Practical constraints. Financial limitations led students to prioritize affordability over ethical considerations, which implemented a perception that ethical travel is accessible only to a niche group of individuals because of its high costs. In addition, limited availability and accessibility of ethical alternatives in certain destinations further directed participants towards unethical options, as ethical choices are more likely to be chosen when more conveniently accessible.

The final factor identified related to Economic-Ideological Factors. Participants suggested that the industry often prioritises profit from regular tourism, resulting in fewer ethical alternatives being developed or promoted. In destinations where lack of ethical infrastructures is relevant, students often selected unethical options by default, normalizing such behaviour as acceptable due to structural limitations rather than ethical preference.

In conclusion, structural constraints highly affect individual's ethical travel behaviour as it establishes whether travellers are able to transform ethical intentions into behaviour, independently of their ethical motivations.

5.7. Contribution of the Research

This dissertation provides several significant contributions to ethical tourism research. First, it shifts the focus from ethical tourism practices towards the constraints of practicing ethical tourism, addressing an underexplored area of the literature. Second, the study provides clearer insights into why the attitude-behaviour gap exists, which are the constraints. Third, the findings provide insights to tourism stakeholders by supporting the development of more accessible ethical tourism options for young travellers.

5.8. Recommendations

5.8.1. Future Research Recommendations

The dissertation outlined multiple future research recommendations. To begin with, as this dissertation employed a qualitative approach limited to personal experiences, future research should adopt quantitative methods to enhance and validate the findings by providing measurable data, identifying patterns, and enabling clear comparisons between constraints.

Another recommendation is to explore the ethical tourism constraints among different demographics groups, as this research solely focused on Gen Z tourism students at NHL Stenden. Future research could examine if similar constraints appear among other age groups, academic programs, or broader populations. This would evaluate whether the constraints identified are influential to all groups or whether additional limitations emerge in different contexts.

A final key recommendation would be for further research to move beyond self-reported data by incorporating observations or experimental methods to analyse if the reported constraints genuinely interfere in ethical tourism behaviour.

5.8.2. Industry Recommendations

This research also identified several recommendations for the tourism sector. One important recommendation is for the industry and tourism organizations to offer more affordable and accessible ethical tourism options. It is essential for the sector to explore budget-friendly ways

to include students in ethical tourism, by implementing student discounts for ethical alternatives or aligning the prices of ethical options with those of regular experiences.

Another recommendation concerns improving transparency around ethical alternatives. The industry is encouraged to use social media channels, such as partnering with ethical travel influencers or showcasing responsible travel online, to clearly communicate how and why their products are ethical. Increasing student's awareness on the background and the impact of these options can help to build confidence towards the authenticity of ethical options while promoting knowledge of ethical tourism.

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Appendix

Appendix A: Research Matrix

Table 3: Research Matrix

Research Matrix

Problem statement: “What are the constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden faces in ethical tourism?”.

Concepts	Explanation and relevance of concept	Research Question	Information	Interview Questions
<p>Concept 1: Intrapersonal Constraints</p>	<p>Intrapersonal constraints referred to the psychological barriers that influence the individual’s behaviour (Corral-Gonzalez et al., 2025). It is relevant because it is the first constraint that individuals have to overcome to practice ethical tourism, such as personality traits, preferences, and motivation.</p>	<p>“What are the <i>intrapersonal constraints</i> Gen Z at NHL Stenden faces in ethical tourism?”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive-Moral factors. • Motivational-Behaviour Factors. • Informational awareness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Thinking back to that trip, did you consider how your choices might affect the environment or local communities? → When planning / travelling, what mattered most to you (e.g., cost, comfort, fun, ethical concerns)? → Were there moments on that trip when you wanted to make a more ethical choice but didn’t? What happened? → What made it difficult to choose the more ethical option in that moment? → Did you ever feel that your individual actions wouldn’t make a difference? → Did you treat that trip as a time to “switch off” from responsibilities? How did that influence your decisions? → Did you ever justify a decision by thinking, “I’m sustainable at home — it’s fine to relax here”? → Did you feel unsure about what was the “right” choice ethically?
<p>Concept 2: Interpersonal Constraints</p>	<p>Interpersonal constraints are the social factors that influence the individual’s behaviour (White, 2008). It is relevant because shows how peer pressure, cultural expectations, and</p>	<p>“What are the <i>interpersonal constraints</i> Gen Z at NHL Stenden faces in ethical tourism?”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social-Normative Factors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → How were decisions made in your travel group during that trip? → Did the group ever want something that didn’t align with your ethical preferences? What did you do? → Did you feel comfortable suggesting more ethical

	<p>social media norms can be a barrier to practice ethical tourism.</p>			<p>alternatives? Why / why not?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Did you feel judged or discouraged when trying to act more ethically? → Did you shift responsibility to others (e.g., “It’s not my call”)? → Did social media influence where you went or what activities you chose on that trip? → Did you go somewhere specifically because it looked good online (e.g., Instagram/TikTok)? → On that trip, did you ever feel pressure to choose things that were more “aesthetic” than ethical? → Did you compare your trip with what you saw online from peers or influencers? → Did social media make it easier or harder to behave ethically on that trip?
<p>Concept 3: Structural Constraints</p>	<p>Structural constraints are the external factors that act as a barrier to practice ethical tourism (Ntovoli et al., 2025). It is relevant because time limitations, lack of information, economic factors, and ideological factors can prevent the individual’s intentions to become a behaviour.</p>	<p>“What are the structural constraints Gen Z at NHL Stenden faces in ethical tourism?”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informational and Access Barriers • Economic and Practical Barriers • Economic-Ideological Factors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → How easy or difficult was it to find responsible options during that trip? → Were there destinations or activities you considered, but ethical alternatives were unavailable / too complex? → On that trip, were ethical options more expensive or less convenient? → Did time, transportation, or distance make it difficult to choose more ethical activities? → During that trip, did you justify certain choices because they supported local jobs?

				→ Did external factors (weather, infrastructure) affect your behaviour?
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Appendix B: Workshop Instructions

Intrapersonal constraints

1) When you think about ethical tourism, what are the first 5 words that comes to mind?

2) Scenario A

You see two tours:

90€- eco-certified

45€- regular

You are a student on budget.

✓ Choose the response that feels MOST like you:

- I choose the cheaper one.
- I struggle but choose the eco one.
- I look for more info first.
- I feel annoyed there's no affordable ethical option.
- I prefer not to think about it — I'm here to relax.

3) Scenario B

You're on holiday with friends. They want to do an activity that harms the environment, but you don't love the idea.

✓ Select:

- I go along — it's majority vote.
- I try to convince them to choose differently.
- I stay behind.
- I tell myself "it's just this once."

4) Scenario C

You see news that technology is improving carbon-neutral travel.

✓ Select:

- Great — the future will fix it.
- Still feels important to act now.
- Unsure.

5) Multiple Constraints

Choose the constraints that apply to you at least sometimes and then from everything you ticked, choose the TOP 3 constraints that feel most true for you (rank them from top (strongest) to bottom (weakest)).

A) Cognitive–Moral

- Comfort or cost often matter more to me than ethics.
- I sometimes feel like there are no better alternatives.
- Travel is my time to relax — I don't think about ethics much.
- I'm sustainable at home, so it evens out.
- Technology will solve these issues eventually.
- I don't feel individually responsible.
- My choices don't make much difference.
- Changing behaviour feels disruptive/uncomfortable.

B) Motivational–Behavioural

- I'm often too busy to research ethical options.
- I'm not very motivated to change travel habits.
- I prioritise my enjoyment — it's my holiday.
- Convenience usually wins.
- I justify unethical choices by thinking tourism helps local economies.

C) Informational

- I don't know enough about ethical tourism.
- I don't know what ethical options exist.

Interpersonal Constraints

- 1) Rank the groups below in order of influence on your travel choices:
(5 = strongest influence)

Group

- 1 Friends

Group

- 2 Parents/family
- 3 Social media
- 4 Partner
- 5 No one / I decide myself
- 6 Other: _____

2) Rate how strongly you feel **social pressure** to travel in a certain way:

Factor	Strength (1-5)
Friends' opinions	1-2-3-4-5
Family expectations	1-2-3-4-5
Social media trends	1-2-3-4-5
Looking “cool” online	1-2-3-4-5
Avoiding judgment	1-2-3-4-5

Why?

Structural Constraints

1) Present random pairs, and choose from each pair, the one that would stop you more from travelling ethically:

1. Lack of information / unclear labelling
2. Limited sustainable options available
3. High cost / financial limitations
4. Time pressure / convenience
5. Distance / accessibility issues
6. Economic-ideological beliefs (e.g., job creation justifies impact)

2) From the three that came out, choose the ONE that would stop you the most:

3) “Why do you feel this barrier affects you the most?”

4) “Can you think of a moment when this barrier actually prevented you from making an ethical choice?”

Appendix C: Interview Script 1

- Introduction

Thank you for taking part in this interview. I’m conducting research for my dissertation on the constraints that Generation Z students at NHL Stenden face when trying to practice ethical tourism.

Your participation is voluntary, and all information will remain anonymous and confidential. There are no right or wrong answers; I’m interested in your personal opinions and experiences. The interview will last around 40–45 minutes, and with your permission, I would like to record it for accuracy.

Do you agree to participate and to the recording of this interview?

- Background information

Could you please briefly describe your background and connection to tourism (for example, studies, interests, travel experiences, etc)?

How often do you travel, and what types of tourism experiences do you usually engage in?

What does ethical tourism mean to you personally?

When did you first become aware of ethical tourism?

How confident do you feel in recognising what is or is not “ethical” while travelling?

Being a NHL Student studying tourism, how do you feel that that influenced your knowledge and choices related to ethical tourism?

- Ethical intention

How important is it for you to act ethically when travelling?

What kinds of behaviours do you consider “ethical” while travelling?

Can you give an example when you consciously tried to make an ethical decision related to tourism? What motivated that choice?

What personal values or beliefs influence your desire to travel ethically?

How these values connect to what you study or learn at NHL Stenden?

Do you ever experience an internal conflict between what you believe is ethical and what you actually do when travelling?

- Intrapersonal constraints

What makes it difficult for you to always act ethically when you travel?

Do you sometimes feel that convenience, comfort, or relaxation become more important than acting ethically?

How informed do you feel about ethical travel options? And where do you get your information?

Do you feel that your actions as one individual do not make much difference?

Are there times when you feel too busy or unmotivated to consider ethical issues when planning a trip?

Have you ever experienced a moment where you know what's right but where doing otherwise? What made you do otherwise?

What motivated you most to choose or avoid ethical options (such as price, comfort, habit, or information)?

What could help you personally to overcome these internal barriers?

- Interpersonal constraints

How do your friends, family, or others influence your travel choices?

Have you ever felt social pressure when travelling? Such as to act ethically or to not worry about it.

Do you think others around you value ethical tourism as much as you?

Can you think of a moment where social expectation made it harder to act ethically?

How does social media shape your travel choices?

Do you feel social media encourages ethical behaviour, or more often, the opposite?

- Structural constraints

What external factors make it difficult to practice ethical tourism (such as price, availability, accessibility, lack of information)?

Have you ever noticed whether ethical tourism options are easy or hard to find when booking trips?

How do time, budget, or convenience affect your ability to travel ethically?

Do you feel that tourism providers or destinations clearly communicate ethical choices?

Are there any situations where you wanted to choose the ethical option but couldn't because of external limitations?

What kind of industry changes do you think could reduce these barriers?

- Intention-Behaviour Gap

Thinking about your last trip, how closely did your actions match your ethical intentions?

What specific factors do you think caused any difference between what you intended and what you actually did?

In your opinion, which type of constraint personally, socially, or structurally (intrapersonal, interpersonal, or structural) has the biggest impact on that gap?

What could help to reduce that gap between your intentions and your behaviour?

What kind of resource would make ethical tourism easier for you personally?

- Closing questions

Overall, what do you think could help Gen Z travellers practice ethical tourism more effectively?

If you could send one message to tourism organizations about ethical tourism, what would it be?

Is there anything else you would like to add that we haven't discussed?

Appendix D: Interview Script 2

1. Can you tell me a bit about yourself and your background in tourism studies?
2. Tell me a bit about your last trip: where did you go and what kind of trips do you usually like to take?
3. When you were planning or during that trip, did you ever think about how your choices affected the environment or local people?
4. Sometimes people want to travel responsibly but end up doing things that aren't perfectly "ethical." Can you remember any moment when you wanted to do something more "ethical" but ended up choosing differently? What was behind that decision?
5. Can you tell me more about what made that difficult?
6. Would you say that was more about things like time, money, or just not knowing what options were out there?
7. When you travel, what usually matters most to you? Is it comfort, price, fun, or doing the right thing?
8. Do you ever feel like small actions — like choosing a hotel or activity — don't make a big difference overall?
9. Some people say travelling is their time to relax, not to think too much about responsibilities. How do you feel about that? Do you relate to that at all, or do you see it differently?
10. Do you feel like you have enough information to make ethical choices when you plan a trip?
11. When you travel with friends or family, how do you usually make decisions together on what to do or where to stay?
12. Have there been times when what the group wanted didn't really match your own values or what you thought was more ethical?
13. What did you do in that situation?
14. How comfortable would you feel suggesting something more sustainable, like avoiding certain activities or paying a bit more for an ethical option?
15. Have you ever felt judged for wanting to be more ethical or sustainable while travelling?
16. How about social media; do you think the kinds of trips people post online influence what you want to do or how you feel about your own travel choices?
17. Thinking back to your last trip again — were there any practical things that made it hard to travel the way you ideally wanted to? For example, maybe ethical options were too expensive, too far away, or hard to find?
18. How much do price and convenience influence your decisions?
19. Sometimes people say: 'At least tourism creates jobs, even if it's not always sustainable.' What do you think about that?

20. Looking back, would you say there's a difference between what you intend to do as an ethical traveller and what actually happens when you travel? What makes it hardest to act according to your values?
21. If you could change something that would make it easier for students like you to travel more ethically, what would it be?
22. And finally, do you think studying tourism at NHL Stenden changes the way you think or behave when you travel?

Appendix E: Interview Script Final

1. To start, could you tell me a bit about yourself and your background in tourism studies?
2. Could you tell me about your last trip — where did you go, who did you travel with, and what was the purpose?
3. Thinking back to that trip, did you consider how your choices might affect the environment or local communities?
4. Before going, did you intend to act ethically on that trip?
Probe: What did "ethical" mean to you in that moment?
5. When planning / travelling, what mattered most to you (e.g., cost, comfort, fun, ethical concerns)?
6. Were there moments on that trip when you wanted to make a more ethical choice but didn't? What happened?
6. What made it difficult to choose the more ethical option in that moment?
7. Did you ever feel that your individual actions wouldn't make a difference?
8. Did you treat that trip as a time to "switch off" from responsibilities? How did that influence your decisions?
9. Did you ever justify a decision by thinking, "I'm sustainable at home — it's fine to relax here"?
10. Did you feel unsure about what was the "right" choice ethically?
11. Did you assume that technology / innovation makes individual ethical behaviour less important?
13. In that trip, did personal enjoyment or convenience outweigh ethical intentions at any point?
14. Did you feel too busy, tired, or overwhelmed to think about being ethical?
15. Were there habits or routines (e.g., how you usually travel) that influenced how you behaved?
16. On that trip, did you feel you had enough information to make ethical choices?
17. Did a lack of information ever prevent you from choosing a more responsible option?
18. How were decisions made in your travel group during that trip?

19. Did the group ever want something that didn't align with your ethical preferences? What did you do?
20. Did you feel comfortable suggesting more ethical alternatives? Why / why not?
21. Did you feel judged or discouraged when trying to act more ethically?
22. Did you shift responsibility to others (e.g., "It's not my call")?
23. Did social media influence where you went or what activities you chose on that trip?
24. Did you go somewhere specifically because it looked good online (e.g., Instagram/TikTok)?
25. On that trip, did you ever feel pressure to choose things that were more "aesthetic" than ethical?
26. Did you compare your trip with what you saw online from peers or influencers?
27. Did social media make it easier or harder to behave ethically on that trip?
28. How easy or difficult was it to find responsible options during that trip?
28. Were there destinations or activities you considered, but ethical alternatives were unavailable / too complex?
30. On that trip, were ethical options more expensive or less convenient?
31. Did time, transportation, or distance make it difficult to choose more ethical activities?
32. During that trip, did you justify certain choices because they supported local jobs?
33. Did external factors (weather, infrastructure) affect your behaviour?
34. Thinking about that trip, is there a gap between what you intended to do ethically and what you actually did?
35. Which kinds of factors during that trip made it hardest to act according to your values — personal preferences, social influence, or external limitations?
36. Based on that experience, what would make it easier for students like you to travel more ethically?
37. Did your tourism studies influence how you acted on that trip?

Appendix F: Coding Table

Table 4: Coding Table

Intrapersonal Constraints		
Cognitive-Moral factors	Other issues have greater importance	you cannot always make the most ethical choice

--

my convenience, time and money weighs heavier

I prefer to think about what I want to do for that moment and get the privilege of still seeing or doing an activity before its gone

I put my comfort and what I want to do in front of ethical considerations

the ethical concerns would be the last of my priorities

we look at things more important to us than ethics

Because comfort and affordability are a priority for me while travelling, and I feel like convenience is a synonym to like affordability and comfort. it's just what I'm seeking for when I go on holiday somewhere.

If I'm obligated to do something, I just do it because there are other priorities and sometimes you cannot just put your principles to the forefront

my work or university travels, it is an obligation of mine, I have to follow them even if I do not agree with it.

I want to travel first, and then ethical concerns and expectations and priorities come after the main motivation

I think in general it is more the comfort and fun my priorities.

tourists travel to have fun and enjoy

“I want to get what I paid for” mindset

I mainly travel for fun, relaxation, or to explore

I could not go, but it was family vacation, and necessary

I prefer that I am not ethical one time and enjoyed it, rather than just not go because I want to be ethical

we had a bit more focus on what we actually wanted to do rather than

		<p>actually considering more ethical practices, I think.</p> <p>it's just much easier to plan something if you don't consider the ethical aspects</p>
	<p>Expressing no alternative to current behaviours</p>	<p>if you go to a really popular museum, it will be crowded. And I cannot control the opening hours</p> <p>There's no other way to go</p> <p>there is not really an ethical way to get there</p> <p>I sometimes feel like there are no better alternatives for sure</p>
	<p>Using escape and relaxation as an excuse for ignoring environmental considerations</p>	<p>because it's just my holiday, so I want to be comfortable</p> <p>sometimes I don't want to think about it, I am on vacations to relax,</p> <p>on holiday I want to enjoy and not worry about ethics</p> <p>I only had one week and wanted to make the most of the vacation</p> <p>it was my only vacation, so I thought that it would be fine if this time we didn't act ethically.</p> <p>you just make an unethical decision just because you want more relaxation</p> <p>I want to switch off my brain, but I do it because I'm trying to get away and have just a relaxing holiday</p>
	<p>Justifying non-sustainable behaviour while travelling</p>	<p>Because also I feel when you're at home, you're also trying to be ethical and you're like behaving well, I guess, because you're not taking any airplanes or anything. So then that one time where you actually take an airplane and everything, then you're like, okay, now I make an exception, and I actually look more for my comfort and affordability.</p> <p>Why should I, as a tourist, not go to the overcrowded places, if the other tourists</p>

		<p>are going?</p> <p>I feel like if more people do it, then I feel it's not that bad of a thing to do</p> <p>other people were going to, so at least I could enjoy something that I really wanted to do, if it is going to be done either way</p> <p>No I didn't search anything prior, but after the travel, I saw them giving food and water to the camels, so that was enough to tranquilized my choice</p> <p>It's more polluting and less ethical environmentally wise, but it also takes a toll on your body if you're not used to it</p> <p>is it bad for environment? Yes. Is it already there? Then use it.</p> <p>also I think if I go or not go, the animal is still going to be there and it's still, maybe it's not driving me, but it's driving another tourist so maybe I will give him like €5 more so he can give the animal more to drink or something and then in my case, it would be OK in my mind.</p> <p>because I am sustainable at home, I can relax on holiday</p>
	Denying responsibility	<p>Work wise I have to because you know it's work</p> <p>Because is only this time, it would be different if I would do it every time, you know?</p> <p>I wouldn't have the flexibility of choosing someplace closer.</p> <p>it's not really, I think, the consumer's fault, but more of the government and the people who are offering it</p> <p>it shouldn't be one person's effort</p>
	Claiming that personal behaviour has little impact	<p>Overtourism is happening there, but then it's more of a problem for a community</p>

		<p>I feel that if I do not do it, then no matter what, is still people going to go, even if it is completely full of tourists</p> <p>individual actions can make a difference, but I'm sceptical about how huge the impact is.</p> <p>my choices individually maybe don't make much difference</p> <p>if I don't do it it's not going to change anything so it's not going to make a big difference</p> <p>the problem is that, not everyone is choosing the responsible action, so why should I do it, and not do things that I want to do, if other people can</p> <p>if they're not doing it, someone else will</p> <p>it would be more ethical to leave houses for families, but I can't really change that</p> <p>it's kind of impossible because it's already an Airbnb, so it's not going to change</p> <p>people say that it's fine if they don't do it, because they are the only one, so it's not going to make a difference.</p> <p>when it comes to like turning it into a collective effort, it's really limited. Because I don't feel that much powerful in this sense</p> <p>I believe that many people disregard these aspects because they say that nobody cares or why do I have to do it if the others don't?</p>
	<p>Internal conflicts, reluctance to take risks, and resistance to changing consumption behaviour</p>	<p>Just simply sticking to the daily basis and ensuring that I do them when I travel because it's just how I am and how I operate</p> <p>I wouldn't say that I was unsure but sometimes is quite difficult to understand if you should adapt to their ethical values, because if go against them, you are being truthful to your it's really hard to be consistent in ethical tourism</p>

		<p>ethical concerns.</p> <p>I think there were times where I had the intention to act ethically, but honestly I did not know if it would be worse if I actually acted on it.</p> <p>There were many times where I was conflicted with what to do, to be honest.</p> <p>I feel like because it's going too much out of what I am willing to do.</p> <p>I don't think it's enough to change my behaviour completely</p> <p>I want to be like respectful and ethical and not the typical mass tourist, but I also paid to go to this place</p> <p>either way, I'm kind of doing something wrong</p> <p>I think it also depends on the places that you go because I think if you go for example to a place where the local people are maybe way more poor or like that the country already has a lot of issues, I think people should be a bit more careful with what they do and what they support.</p> <p>what I think is ethical might be different from you</p> <p>Maybe someone's beliefs are different than mine because of their culture, and if we want to say also religion</p> <p>where do you draw the line for ethical tourism?</p> <p>conflict with yourself because you know that it's not ethical for you to do, but you would love to do it</p> <p>then people just don't know about it and they just want to stick to their normal</p>
<p>Motivational- Behaviour Factors</p>	<p>Being too occupied to change behaviours</p>	<p>I'm often too busy to research ethical options</p> <p>Most of the times you just do not have the time to make it more ethical.</p>

		<p>I don't have the time to just to do the right thing and just considering ethical options.</p> <p>I think it does take more time, more effort to plan ethical options.</p> <p>I am a student, I do not have time</p>
	<p>Lack of motivation</p>	<p>Looking it up is easy, but I didn't really do the effort</p> <p>main motivation is to travel</p> <p>I don't think I had this intention, of ok, I'm not doing this, not doing that because of ethical reasons, only because we didn't feel like it</p> <p>I actually prioritise ethical considerations, but not every time and not intentionally I think, depending on the situation.</p> <p>I think we just went with it, I didn't check information before, it was just what we wanted to do</p> <p>I don't think I go out of my way to look for just ethical activities</p> <p>I didn't really think about being ethical in traveling itself</p> <p>because I did not have the ethical intention while making the trip</p>
	<p>Egoism</p>	<p>if I would be somewhere only for a day and I don't have a chance to come back, then in that case, I would probably stay if it's something I want to see or want to experience.</p> <p>And if I really want to go to, then I don't choose to go somewhere closer because it's ethically better.</p> <p>I won't prejudicated myself for that.</p> <p>So I prefer to get my chance of seeing it, even if it is unethical, rather than giving that spot to someone else</p>

		<p>I don't prioritise the ethical part. I prioritise me as a tourist because yeah, I'm missing out on this</p> <p>I'm like focusing only on me. So I'm being kind of egoistic in those situations.</p> <p>Humans are selfish and they are always going to go for what they want</p> <p>If people stop travelling because they don't want to participate in overtourism and unethical behaviours, then I am not going to have a job.</p> <p>I will probably still join, if I think it's something that I really would love to do, even if unethical.</p> <p>I know maybe it wasn't an ethical decision, but I still went</p> <p>if I don't go, people are still going to go, and I will be missing out. So I prefer to go, even if that is not the best option</p> <p>I want to do this and that, but it's not really ethical, but you just want to do it</p>
	Convenience preferences	<p>I have people that I want to visit and they happen to live there, so I put my preferences first</p> <p>convenience weighs heavier for me than ethics.</p> <p>I feel like we just choose whatever is quicker</p> <p>I always try to make it cheaper for myself</p> <p>I prefer to have an easier trip rather than everything being 100% ethical</p> <p>I don't want to spend hours on looking for something that I want to go do</p> <p>it's more expensive and it takes more time and I'm less comfortable, I will obviously pick the other option, even if it is less ethical.</p> <p>I saw this possibility close and accessible, I said why not?</p>

		<p>it's faster though I know it's more polluting, but it's less tiring than a train trip that long</p> <p>I book early and don't think about ethics</p> <p>we just book it conforming our preferences, if it is an ethical option great, if it is regular, then that's fine too.</p>
	<p>Compensating unethical behaviour through perceived benefits of tourism</p>	<p>Like if we think about the fact that there would be less tourists, the local community will suffer from that, especially in COVID. Many businesses suffered from that and even had to close because there were no tourists coming anymore.</p> <p>overtourism may harm the local community, but it also brings benefits to it, in the sense of creating jobs and people actually being able to finance their own lives.</p> <p>tourism maintains the island alive</p> <p>the problem is that tourism promotes jobs. People, a lot of people depend on tourism</p> <p>if the business doesn't go anymore, the guy would lose is job and we don't know what would happen to the camels</p> <p>There is a lot of places that survive based on tourism, most of the times overtourism, which I think it might be considered unethical.</p> <p>I would prefer to act unethical while travelling if that means that I am helping someone keep the job</p> <p>When you look at Bali, for example, half of the economy is depending on tourism. It creates jobs, it creates knowledge, it also creates money.</p>
<p>Informational awareness</p>	<p>Limited knowledge and awareness</p>	<p>I feel if I would be having a solid knowledge that it is for sure harming the environment, I wouldn't feel uncomfortable speaking about it</p> <p>Definitely people need to be more informed.</p>

I didn't know anything about the impact and carbon footprint and sustainability and all the other ethical dilemmas around it.

lack of awareness in general in the society

But most people are not aware of the culture and the importance of it.

was not aware that I was being part of something that for me, is not correct to do with animals.

main thing is I don't know how things work

if I am uninformed then I have no knowledge behind my travel decisions.

I didn't have much awareness about ethical tourism and activities

I think the doubt comes when I am not informed enough on the topic

Looking back maybe I should have researched a bit more about it and about its ethical side of this experience.

if I am not well informed about ethical travel, then of course, I will not have knowledge about the ethical options available

if I knew better, I would take public transport

I would be completely unaware and so it just showed me that I need to be careful at certain areas.

you will end up having a gap but the size of the gap, it depends on how prepared you are or like how aware you are

was most more of an impulsive decision taken in the moment, so I didn't do much research about it.

just feel that I don't know enough or have the information to be sure about my decision

also knowing more about it because some things I probably don't even think

		about, that are easier to change than I think
	Ignorance	<p>you just end up in some place which you didn't intend to be, and it is super crowded. And, honestly, you might think that, oh actually that's interesting so, let me stay here</p> <p>To be honest, I still go in an unethical way.</p> <p>Because my dad has an apartment there, so we always stay there. So its just easier to take two planes, even knowing that its wrong.</p> <p>I know that flying is not good for the environment, but yeah, it's not something that really stopped me from like doing that trip</p> <p>I wanted to explore a new place, I wanted to meet my friend, and I wanted to be somewhere in the sun, so I still went knowing that it was wrong.</p>

Interpersonal Constraints

Social-Normative Factors	Tendency to shift responsibility onto others	<p>It wasn't fully on me what I did</p> <p>Yeah, I think we all shift responsibilities to other people.</p> <p>I think people excuse their bad behaviour conforming the amount of people that is doing them</p>
	Societal norms, peer pressure, and expectations from social interactions	<p>if I'm with someone else, I cannot only consider myself.</p> <p>friends and then equally parent's family because those are the people I travel with. So obviously they are a big influence</p> <p>I was also like looking at locals if they do it and if they did it then I did the same.</p> <p>Because we all follow each other, so it tend to mimic what others are doing.</p> <p>there was a buffet and everyone was eating and I was one of them because I was hungry you know and you cannot</p>

		<p>just say oh I don't support having open buffet and I'm not going to eat there</p> <p>if everyone does this, then I should too</p> <p>they all went and I was like the only one saying I'm not going to do it. And I think at the end I had to go.</p> <p>People normally follow one another, so if tourists would behave ethically when travelling, I think everyone would start following that behaviour, like nobody would question it.</p> <p>If it was in a group, and they were doing something, then I think I would probably ignore my ethical concerns and just do it</p> <p>if I travel with friends, I don't want to do things on my own so I would always stick to with what they do</p> <p>if my partner nags me about it continuously, then I will most likely go</p> <p>the people around and the place where you live, so surely, they influence my decisions.</p> <p>It is important to satisfy everybody's necessities and interests as well.</p> <p>because other people did it and you also want to experience it</p> <p>I would suggest ethical options, but most votes count</p> <p>I would feel too awkward if I was the only one not doing it, even if I thought it was wrong</p> <p>the feeling that I have from the latest generation is you always have to copy someone else, someone that you think it's cool and most of the time those people make really bad choices in my opinion</p>
	<p>Family expectations, social stigma toward ethical behaviour, and the tendency to compare one's travel choices</p>	<p>if I'm thinking about going to a place, and then I maybe say to my mom or something, and then she'll say, no because I know that place has this and this, or you shouldn't go to this place</p>

		<p>because of that, then I definitely will reconsider my choice.</p> <p>I actually do feel that I would be judged</p> <p>it's always what the parents decide, so I do not have much choice</p> <p>nobody wants to believe you that you only didn't go because of that, they will say that it was because you did not have time or something. So, in that case, you're it's kind of like a must.</p> <p>with family, it's really hard to do your own stuff and they're not willing to understand.</p>
	<p>Social media influence</p>	<p>if you just plan your trips according to the standards of your influencers then you have to give up on some ethical considerations in a way</p> <p>In our generation, the first thing that we do when we travel, we look for TikTok videos of places</p> <p>I also think because of that a lot of influencers, they want to find something new and they maybe, I don't know, go on top of like a very important touristic site where you usually are not allowed to film or something just because of clicks. And then you end up in the unethical part of social media when you travel.</p> <p>you think everyone needs to know what you're doing at every moment</p> <p>I think nowadays social media influences it a lot more of where I want to go</p> <p>Because of social media, the same post that I saw and my friends saw that made us go there, other people saw it too, and everyone wants to go there which makes it overcrowded and unethical</p> <p>I would prefer people didn't post because it gets overcrowded</p> <p>that's difficult because the person just wants to share where they went and to show what they've been doing. but it's</p>

		<p>not really ethical in the point of view of the community or the place</p> <p>what you see and what you're getting from and how you get influenced by that, basically you build it</p> <p>if people have the opportunity to go do something that others did or posted online, they are going to do it, because we always want to compare each other to others</p> <p>I feel like social media also, because of the fact that it draws a lot of attention to one location, a lot of people start going there.</p> <p>If you just really want to do it because you are influenced by someone else then this is the dangerous part of social media in my opinion it can lead to something bad in terms of ethical considerations.</p> <p>Also because with the social media today, we most of the time we only see one of the sides of the situation and you don't see the other one.</p> <p>you shape your own social media environment.</p> <p>I see a place online which looks nice, so I want to go. But a lot of other people have the same idea, so at the end the place is just overcrowded, and the destination doesn't know how to deal with the amount of tourists.</p>
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Structural Constraints		
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Informational and Access Barriers	Not being correctly informed about ethical vacation alternatives	<p>when you check some places, especially online, you see only the positive aspects of them. No one shows you, oh yeah, it's crowded and it's like full of people or like animals are tortured and you know</p> <p>sometimes, there isn't really a better alternative, because both are going to have their pros and cons.</p>
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	<p>Insufficient labelling and information</p>	<p>you've got to go find the information for yourself because it is not easily in front of you.</p> <p>if people had more information and more options about ethical choices, then is almost impossible that more tourists would not participate in that, simply because of you know, the higher you promote something, also the higher people will participate in it.</p> <p>Companies should provide more information, that's for sure. But yeah, also like tourism students in that sense, then yes, schools should inform them better.</p> <p>there was not information about ethical options</p> <p>the information is not normally very easy to access for the ones that doesn't sell that often, that being the ethical options.</p> <p>it makes it a lot harder to find things like, what can I do that is ethical and all of that. And I feel like there's not enough information about that</p> <p>With the tour guide there, he didn't really say that there were actions that we did that would be like unethical. We went to look at different places and went also like into some caves. But he never told us like, yeah, this is not ethical to do or like he never really talked about ethical things.</p> <p>I feel like is just there, they don't really communicate those with a free will, let's say, you have to ask for it</p>
	<p>Inadequate availability of ethical tourism options</p>	<p>limited sustainable options available because sometimes even if you want to do it, you can't</p> <p>I think maybe if options would be there more and easier, then I wouldn't need more time to research them</p>

		I don't think ethical options were available
Economic and Practical Barriers	Financial limitations	<p>you have your own limitation of how much you can spend or when you can do it.</p> <p>the more affordable is always better for a student.</p> <p>as a student, some things you're not willing to pay more for</p> <p>sometimes I don't have financial space for ethical choice</p> <p>if there are ethical options, if you do not have the money, then its not even relevant that they are available. I would feel even worse if it were available and I just couldn't afford it.</p> <p>for students it's too expensive and too much to plan</p> <p>I would act more unethical because I don't have the money to act ethical</p> <p>I know many people that would rather pick the ethical choice over the unethical one, but as you said It's also always the most expensive one and for us, we don't have a fixed income to sustain that,</p> <p>like if I had a higher income, I wouldn't have any problems, but in this situation that I'm now, it's not that it matters more, but I am more limited under this aspect</p>
	High costs and expensive tourism services	<p>I know often for many people it's a case that they would love to do it, but then I cannot because the price of it.</p> <p>I'm annoyed that there is not a more affordable ethical option.</p> <p>when you try to make less impact, you see additional fees on things</p> <p>if they're sustainable or ethical, they are really expensive and not affordable for an average person</p>

		<p>even if they advertise, they are so expensive that people prefer to choose the cheaper options</p> <p>ethical options are always more expensive, that's a reason why its not as normalised or popular than regular options.</p> <p>I feel like it's hard to make more ethical decisions when it costs more.</p> <p>they have an option where you can pay more in order for the flight to be less harmful. However, its like 600€ extra which, as a student, is impossible.</p> <p>ethical options are basically inaccessible or very limited as a choice, because it is so expensive. So you basically have to rely on the unethical choice or completely change your mind and forget about your travel plans.</p> <p>If it was more accessible, economically wise, I think more people would pick that choice.</p> <p>if it would be more expensive but more ethical if I'm being really honest, I think I always choose for the cheaper option.</p> <p>You want to act right but then you have to pay the price</p>
	Time pressures	<p>if I have to do something that's going to take me double as long then I am not going to do it.</p> <p>we could have done the activities with the probably public transportation, but it would have taken us double the time to go</p> <p>spending all those hours in train instead of doing it quickly with plane.</p> <p>if it's not too time consuming, it's also more likely to be chosen by not only students, but everyone</p> <p>I will do with a regular one because I'm not there for a long time.</p>
	Distance and accessibility barriers	<p>I couldn't practice it as much as I would want to, or as easily I could do here in</p>

		<p>the Netherlands, let's say. So yeah, there I couldn't, even if I wanted to.</p> <p>if it is not easy to reach, then tourists just don't bother.</p> <p>the last thing I want to do move around by car. But in that case, it was needed because of the type of trip we had planned</p> <p>But it depends, I think, on the distance for sure.</p> <p>in some places it's difficult to be more ethical, if you are on holidays in some specific places</p> <p>I feel like also obviously accessibility makes it harder to practice ethical tourism</p>
<p>Economic-Ideological Factors</p>	<p>Highlighting industries benefits from carbon-emitting options</p>	<p>for the companies the profit is bigger than the constraints.</p> <p>The industry pushes entrepreneurs or companies to make money.</p> <p>They don't do nothing in relation to that, because it drives more money.</p> <p>the Global industry the times are still raw to push ethical options.</p> <p>companies always have the purpose to sell you their products, so they're never going to say our product is not ethical</p> <p>the majority are big multinational companies, which and whose only purpose is to make money pretty much. And I believe that ethical tourism, ethical anything, and ethical choices, they don't sell or at least they don't sell as much as the unethical ones, probably.</p>
	<p>External environmental conditions (e.g., weather, infrastructure)</p>	<p>the infrastructure generally is not so well developed, of course. And there's like trash everywhere. And I was so desperately looking for trash cans. And then like throwing away your trash just like the locals do on the ground. I mean,</p>

		<p>you have to do it too because if there are no other options</p> <p>in Morrocco they don't recycle, so I couldn't do anything about that.</p>
	Limited accessibility and financial restrictions	<p>if you want to maybe decide to go to a place or visit a place that is more ethically, sometimes you have to actively choose it, in the sense that it is not easily accessible.</p>

Appendix G: Transcripts

Not published for participant's protection